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MASTER THESIS

Power consumption properties of modern multicore server CPUs

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Declaration of Authorship

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“If you’re too sloppy, then you never get reproducible results, and then you can never draw any conclusions; but if you are just a little sloppy, then when you see something startling, you say, ‘Oh, my God, what did I do, what did I do different this time?’ And if you really accidentally varied only one parameter, you nail it down, and that’s exactly what happened [to produce new experimental discoveries]. So I called it the ‘Principle of Limited Sloppiness’.”

Max Delbrück

Abstract

In the age of exascale computing, the importance of understanding power dissipation and energy efficiency is undisputed. This thesis attempts to delve into the dynamics and behaviour of power and energy dissipation in selected modern server grade computing nodes. A preliminary goal is to assess whether the power models of yesteryears still hold in the face of these newer architectures. We employ comprehensive microbenchmarks, differentiating between performance bound and memory saturated computational workloads and their power draw. Modern CPU architectures allow for powerful, SIMD enhanced instruction sets such as *Advanced Vector Extensions (AVX)*, which play a major role in determining power dissipation and code scalability. We see that for the purpose of minimizing energy to solution, the choice of instruction set and number of active cores to be used is not arbitrary but depends on code characteristics as well. Moreover, we investigate the energy costs of elementary operations, such as moving data through the memory hierarchy via cacheline transfers and performing numerical operations involving *double-precision (DP)* flops. Our investigation extends to predicting the energy and power profiles for a given loop kernel. As a refinement, we employ a statistical model using non-linear function approximation. By providing data encompassing different benchmarks and system parameters, we arrive at an estimate for power and energy consumption tailored to a specific node.

Zusammenfassung

Im Zeitalter des Exascale-Computings ist das Verständnis für Leistungsabgabe und Energieeffizienz von entscheidender Bedeutung. Diese Arbeit versucht, in die Dynamik und das Verhalten von Leistungs- und Energieabgabe in ausgewählten modernen Server-Computing-Knoten einzutauchen. Ein vorläufiges Ziel besteht darin zu prüfen, ob die Leistungsmodelle vergangener Jahre angesichts dieser neueren Architekturen immer noch Bestand haben. Wir verwenden umfassende Mikrobenchmarks und differenzieren zwischen leistungsgebundenen und speichergesättigten Berechnungsworkloads sowie ihrem Energieverbrauch. Moderne CPU-Architekturen ermöglichen leistungsstarke, SIMD-optimierte Befehlssätze wie *Advanced Vector Extensions (AVX)*, die eine entscheidende Rolle bei der Bestimmung von Leistungsabgabe und Code-Skalierbarkeit spielen. Wir erkennen, dass die Wahl des Befehlssatzes und der Anzahl der aktiven Kerne nicht willkürlich ist, sondern auch von den Eigenschaften des Codes abhängt, um die Energieeffizienz zu maximieren. Darüber hinaus untersuchen wir die Energiekosten elementarer Operationen, wie das Verschieben von Daten durch die Speicherhierarchie mittels Cacheline-Transfers und die Durchführung numerischer Operationen mit *doppelt genauen (DP)* Flops. Unsere Untersuchung erstreckt sich auf die Vorhersage der Energie- und Leistungsprofile für eine gegebene Schleifenoperation. Als Verfeinerung verwenden wir ein statistisches Modell unter Verwendung einer nichtlinearen Funktionsapproximation. Durch Bereitstellung von Daten, die verschiedene Benchmarks und Systemparameter, erhalten wir eine Schätzung für den Leistungs- und Energieverbrauch, die auf einen bestimmten Knoten zugeschnitten ist.

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List of Abbreviations

AVX	A dvanced V ector eX tensions
SMT	S imultaneous M ulti T hreading
TDP	T hermal D esign P ower
NUMA	N on U niform M emory A ccess
SNC	S ub N uma C lustering
NPS	N odes P er S ocket
DP	D ouble P recision
HPC	H igh P erformance C omputing
SIMD	S ingle I nstruction M ultiple D ata
SSE	S treaming S IMD E xtensions
EDP	E nergy D elay P roduct
DRAM	D ynamic R andom A ccess M emory
FMA	F used M ultiply A dd
FLOP	F loating P oint O peration
CPU	C entral P rocessing U nit
LLC	L owest L evel C ache
OI	O perational I ntensity
CPI	C ycles P er I nstruction
IPC	I nstructions P er C ycle
CG	C onjugate G radient
CCX	C ore C omplex
CL	C ache L ine
DGEMM	D ouble (precision) G eneral M atrix M ultiply
DVFS	D ynamic V oltage (and) F requency S caling
DIMMs	D ual I n-line M emory M odules

List of Symbols

W_0^{base}	Baseline power constant term	[W]
W_1^{base}	Baseline power linear term	[W][GHz] ⁻¹
W_2^{base}	Baseline power quadratic term	[W][GHz] ⁻²
W_0^{core}	Core power constant term	[W]
W_1^{core}	Core power linear term	[W][GHz] ⁻¹
W_2^{core}	Core power quadratic term	[W][GHz] ⁻²
β_0	L2 cache power coefficient	[nW][CL] ⁻¹
β_1	L3 cache power coefficient	[nW][CL] ⁻¹
γ	Instruction power coefficient	[nW][I] ⁻¹
μ	Flop throughput	[MFlops][cy] ⁻¹
β	Main memory Bandwidth	[Mbytes][s] ⁻¹
ϵ_{mem}	Main memory energy per cacheline	[J][CL] ⁻¹
J	Jacobian matrix	-

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The relentless pursuit of performance improvements in modern computing has given rise to the era of multicore processors, where a single chip can house multiple processing cores, each capable of executing multiple threads simultaneously. This ever-increasing demand for faster and more efficient computing has driven the need for a comprehensive understanding of power consumption in modern multicore server CPUs. As applications become more complex and demanding, power-efficient design is not just a matter of preference but a crucial necessity.

Understanding power consumption properties in modern processors is not only of academic interest but also has a multitude of real-world applications seen in optimizing system performance, prolonging device lifespan, and reducing the carbon footprint of data centers. Data centers are major energy consumers, accounting for an estimated 1.8% of global electricity consumption in 2022 [13]. This energy consumption is driven by the high power requirements of the servers, storage systems, and cooling infrastructure that make up data centers. Since servers are the core components of data centers, their power efficiency of great interest. Although power consumption can vary significantly depending on the type of server, its workload, and its configuration, a typical server rack can consume up to 50kW of power [15]. The world's current largest supercomputer system, Frontier, consumes an astonishing 52.2 MW [30], with the facility having an overall thermal capacity of upto 85 MW. As a consequence, energy efficiency lends itself to a more important role when discussing the current state of HPC.

While achievements in energy efficiency may be being made, it is imperative to note that computational workloads in many scientific and engineering domains are also increasing rapidly. Furthermore, with the increasing price of energy in Europe, the importance of understanding power consumption is only compounded.

Thus in this thesis we embark on a journey to explore the intricacies of power measurement and modeling for server CPUs in the exascale era. The inclusion of modern architectural features such as register vectorization and configurable cache coherent memory domains makes power dissipation a multifaceted phenomenon. We aim to study power draw properties, and through micro-benchmarks and experimentation, assign power costs associated to specific CPU events. We delve into the complex behaviour of nodes, examining their architecture, features, and power-saving technologies. Additionally, we will explore the methodologies for accurately measuring power consumption in various operational scenarios. Through rigorous experimentation and analysis, we seek to build models that capture the complex relationship between workloads, system configurations, and power dissipation behavior in these machines.

CPUs with the current EPYC architecture. NPS also divides the memory into smaller NUMA nodes, and in essence works the same way.

- Simultaneous Multithreading (SMT):
 - Often implemented on x86 architectures as Intel's Hyper-Threading Technology or AMD's SMT, Simultaneous Multithreading enables a single physical core to execute multiple threads concurrently. Each thread has its own set of architectural registers and program counter, allowing the CPU to switch between threads quickly.
 - Improved Resource Utilization: SMT often enhances overall CPU throughput by utilizing idle resources during pipeline stalls or memory latency. It allows better utilization of execution units and can lead to increased performance, especially in scenarios with diverse instruction mixes.
- L3 victim cache:
 - A victim cache is a type of cache that is designed to store lines evicted from a higher-level cache, typically the L1 cache, due to a cache miss. The purpose of a victim cache is to reduce the negative impact of cache misses by providing a small, fast cache where recently evicted lines can be stored temporarily. This helps to mitigate the performance penalty associated with fetching the same data from the slower main memory.
 - An exclusive victim cache is a specific type of victim cache that is used in certain cache architectures. In an exclusive victim cache, the lines that are stored in the victim cache are distinct from those stored in the higher-level cache. This means that a line evicted from the higher-level cache due to a cache miss is placed exclusively in the victim cache and does not exist in the higher-level cache at the same time.
- Power Management:
 - Dynamic Frequency Scaling: Many modern server CPUs incorporate dynamic frequency scaling, adjusting the clock frequency based on the workload. This allows for better power efficiency by reducing power consumption during periods of lower demand.
 - Modern Intel CPUs dynamically downscale the frequency of the CPU when AVX instructions are used. Since the Haswell architecture, processors executing non-vectorized instructions do not automatically downscale when other cores on the same socket are downscaled due to AVX instructions (Gottschlag and Bellosa [2019]).
- System Uncore
 - The "uncore" of a CPU is a term used by Intel that refers to the parts of a microprocessor that are not part of the core, which is responsible for executing instructions in the instruction set architecture.
 - It includes levels of cache that are not directly inside the CPU cores, such as the L3, which is shared among cores. It also consists of Memory Controllers and pathway Interconnects. On newer Intel architectures the uncore has a configurable clock speed.

1.3 Related work

While a multitude of different power models for predicting application energy consumption on CPUs exist, they generally are part of either of two general approaches to modelling on *DVFS (Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling)* processors. These are processors that use a power management technique wherein supply voltage and frequency are dynamically adjusted 'as needed' during runtime based on its workload [17], or according to an external performance policy. They generally exploit the linear relationship of power consumption primarily depends linearly on the operating frequency of a machine. The first category includes analytical models that begin with consideration of power dissipation based on digital circuit behaviour. These can be understood as a 'bottom-up' approach, with characteristics being derived from physical considerations of power behaviour with circuit voltage or current. In such a model, one could describe the dynamic power consumption as a function of both voltage and frequency as

$$P_{\text{dynamic}}(V, f) = k_{\text{dynamic}} \cdot \alpha \cdot V^2 \cdot f \quad (1.1)$$

where k is a generic fit coefficient and α is the switching activity probability [21]. The static power could be described as a product of leakage current with supply voltage as

$$P_{\text{static}}(V, I_{\text{leak}}) = k_{\text{static}} \cdot V^2 \cdot I_{\text{leak}} \quad (1.2)$$

The exact constants and considered factors would depend on the specific model and architecture of the machine being modelled. A study by Vogeleer et al. [2014] used findings concerning leakage current and dynamic power dissipation (Skadron et al. [2004]) to then predict total power as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\text{total}}(V, f) &= P_{\text{leak}} + P_{\text{dynamic}} \\ &= \Gamma \cdot V \cdot P_{\text{dynamic}} + P_{\text{dynamic}} \\ &= (1 + \Gamma \cdot V) \cdot \eta \cdot \alpha \cdot f \cdot V^2 \end{aligned} \quad (1.3)$$

where Γ includes temperature dependence of leakage current and η is a system coefficient. An assumption of voltage being linearly dependent to target frequency would then suggest that static power dissipation shows cubic dependence on operational frequency, and dynamic power dissipation would display quartic behaviour over frequency scaling. The second category involves a more 'top-down' approach, wherein one considers the entire power consumption of the CPU, and uses data parameter fitting to achieve a sufficiently good model estimation. This leads to a heuristic model that employs curve fitting with the goal of deriving a continuous approximation to discrete data. Rauber et al. [2014] suggested an assumption of linear dependence of power from operating frequency using unknown parameters. The approximation they considered was as follows

$$P_{\text{total}}(f) = a + b \cdot f^{1+\chi} \quad (1.4)$$

where the fitting parameter a could be interpreted as a static part of power dissipation that is frequency independent, and b captures a dynamic part which displays the DVFS characteristics we would expect. The χ parameter could take several fixed values so that the aforementioned fitted parameters could be determined by the least

squares method. However, one should mention that these values of course would depend on the specific benchmark being used since they would differ for different computational and memory access behaviour. Since we do not have a sufficiently accurate way to measure supply voltage in the form of an external voltmeter, we consider the latter, 'top-down' approach to power modelling.

1.4 Previous work

Hager et al. [2013] provided a heuristic, empirically achieved power model based on a second order polynomial in clock frequency. This was then refined to include the uncore clock, as well as fit parameters based on parallel efficiency (Hofmann et al. [2018]). First, the assumption of a static "baseline" power component for the whole die, which is a function of only the clock speed of the uncore.

$$P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{Uncore}}) = W_0^{\text{base}} + W_1^{\text{base}} \cdot f_{\text{Uncore}} + W_2^{\text{base}} \cdot f_{\text{Uncore}}^2 \quad (1.5)$$

On current generation Intel CPUs, the Uncore clock is a configurable and measurable property. Here, the W_* coefficients are fit parameters. Additionally, they had assumed the existence of an additional power per active core, with both static and dynamic power contributions, that are a function of only the core clock speed.

$$P_{\text{core}}(f, n) = (W_0^{\text{core}} + W_1^{\text{core}} \cdot f_{\text{core}} + W_2^{\text{core}} \cdot f_{\text{core}}^2) \epsilon(n)^\alpha \quad (1.6)$$

Here, n denotes the number of active cores. This expression also includes a damping factor, $\epsilon(n)^\alpha$ wherein $\epsilon(n)$ describes a kernel's parallel efficiency at n cores and α is a fitted parameter. The justification of being that in the presence of a memory bottleneck, the core power dissipation still increases, but not as rapidly because the of *Instructions Per Cycle (IPC)*, or instruction throughput, of the whole chip stagnates. When fitted for previous generations of processors, it was observed that generally the linear terms W_1 were small compared to the quadratic coefficients W_2 . Also, the baseline power W_0 seemed to be generally independent of code characteristics and core clock. This makes the power dissipation seem more convincingly quadratic. For example, if the behaviour inherently follows a quadratic trend but the first order term dominates the equation, the model might not accurately represent the true quadratic nature of the data. Generally this would result in poor predictions outside the range of fitted data, but this would not be of primary concern since CPU behaviour at very low clock speeds is rather unpredictable. Finally, this provides a complete model for the chip

$$P_{\text{chip}} = P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{Uncore}}) + n \cdot P_{\text{core}}(f_{\text{Core}}, n) \quad (1.7)$$

As compared to the capabilities of similar proposed models, this approximation now includes Uncore clock frequency as a model parameter, as well as a scaling factor that would account for lower than expected core power dissipation in saturating code kernels. Of course, this would require additional fitting for every new kernel introduced. The choice of a quadratic polynomial does not necessarily follow from any sort of physical assumption as described above (1.3), nor with a exponential heuristic form as seen here (1.4). It was observed that neither of these forms seemed to improve fit accuracy. Practically speaking, the linear adjustment of voltage to frequency occurs only when permitted to do so. A manufacturer set limit on voltage control would lead to higher order power-frequency behaviour not being observed.

In conjunction with their *Execution Cache Memory (ECM)* model [22], they had also predicted an optimum frequency with which one achieves a minimum energy dissipation.

$$f_{\text{opt}} = \sqrt{\frac{W_0^{\text{base}} + n \cdot W_0^{\text{core}}}{W_2^{\text{base}} + n \cdot W_2^{\text{core}}}} \quad (1.8)$$

for a configuration of a fixed uncore clock equal to that of the core, and a given number of active cores, n .

1.5 Thesis organization

We begin by introducing our testbed, with machine properties of interest, as well as our measurement methodology in Chapter 2. Following this, Chapter 3 discusses categorization using code characteristics, and defining properties of types of code. One may also visualize this compartmentalization using naive roofline diagrams plotted for a given node. Next, we take a look at general trends in energy dissipation found in modern architectures, as well as a few notable power draw characteristics. We then consider its interplay with performance since this is a primary concern in HPC systems. In conjunction, we then assess and validate the previous power model on these newer chips. The DRAM power draw is also of interest, and is measured with different configurations of memory movement. Chapter 5 attempts to break down the various parts of a loop streaming kernel from memory, into elementary operations through micro-benchmarking, allowing for an elementization of power and energy costs for various operations such as flops and main memory cacheline transfers. This allows us to arrive at a first, qualitative model that attempts to predict energy consumption of a given computational kernel. Lastly, we try a statistical approach using Gauss Newton iterations for a non-linear model of power consumption. We use data from various assembly benchmarks with different machine configurable parameters. Here we will consider more intricate parameters such as inter-cache data transfers and retired instruction throughput.

An artifact appendix, containing the data, scripts and code used in the thesis are presented in this [online repository](#).

Chapter 2

Test bed and measurement tools

In the following section we list out the nodes used in our microbenchmarks. These machines are part of the test-cluster of NFR@FAU used for porting software to new CPU architectures and running measurement tests. Since they are not production machines, we have a lot more leeway in changing system configurations. For our purposes, this primarily includes Uncore frequency selection and Sub-NUMA clustering configurations.

2.1 Intel machines

2.1.1 Cascade Lake Test System

Cascade Lake [27], introduced by Intel in April 2019, is a server-grade CPU microarchitecture that stands as the successor to the renowned Skylake architecture. While both Cascade Lake and Skylake utilize a 14nm FinFET manufacturing process, Cascade Lake's optimized process enables higher clock speeds and enhanced performance.

"casclakesp2" node

The "casclakesp2" node consists of two sockets of Intel Xeon "Cascade Lake" Gold 6248 CPUs, with 20 cores each and SMT enabled. This chip has a base frequency of 2.50 GHz and a TDP of 150W. The *thermal design power (TDP)*, or colloquially, the thermal design point of a chip, is the power consumption under the maximum theoretical load [28]. To determine peak performance in terms of double precision flops at base clock, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{\text{peak}} &= n_{\text{cores}} \cdot f_{\text{base}} \cdot I_{\text{cycle}} \cdot m_{\text{FMA}} \cdot \frac{W}{64} \text{GFlops/s} \\
 &= 20 \cdot 2.5 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 8 \text{GFlops/s} \\
 &= 1.60 \text{TFlops/s}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

where n_{cores} is the number of cores, f_{base} is the operating base frequency, I_{cycle} is the floating point operations possible per cycle with an adder and a multiplier, m_{FMA} represents the fused multiply add factor and finally W denotes the width of the widest vector register ops, here, 512 for AVX 512 units on the chip. For theoretical maximum

memory bandwidth, one has

$$\begin{aligned} B_{\text{peak}} &= f_{\text{mem}} \cdot b_{\text{width}} \cdot N_{\text{channels}} \\ &= 2.933 \cdot 8 \cdot 6 \text{ GBytes/s} \\ &= 140.78 \text{ GBytes/s} \end{aligned}$$

where f_{mem} is the maximum storage speed of the DDR4 memory of the chip, b_{width} is the number of bytes of width, and N_{channels} is the number of memory channels.

2.1.2 Ice Lake Test Systems

Ice Lake [32] is Intel's codename for the 10th generation Intel Core mobile and 3rd generation Xeon Scalable server processors based on the Sunny Cove microarchitecture. Ice Lake is built on Intel's 10 nm+ manufacturing process, a refined version of the 10 nm technology used in previous generations. This improved process allows for smaller transistor sizes, enabling more transistors to be packed onto a single chip. This, in turn, leads to better performance and efficiency. These Sunny Cove chips feature redesigned execution units, improved instruction handling, and enhanced memory management. These improvements translate into faster single-threaded performance and improved multitasking capabilities.

"icx36" node

The icx36 node consists of a dual socket Intel Xeon Platinum 8360Y CPU. As the name suggests, it's based on Intel's Ice Lake architecture with a core count of 36 per socket with configurable SNC. It has an operating base clock of 2.4 GHz with a maximum turbo clock of 3.5 GHz. We then have

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\text{peak}} &= n_{\text{cores}} \cdot f_{\text{base}} \cdot I_{\text{cycle}} \cdot m_{\text{FMA}} \cdot \frac{W}{64} \\ &= 36 \cdot 2.4 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 8 \text{ GFlops/s} \\ &= 2.76 \text{ TFlops/s} \end{aligned}$$

and for the memory bandwidth

$$\begin{aligned} B_{\text{peak}} &= f_{\text{mem}} \cdot d \cdot b_{\text{width}} \cdot N_{\text{channels}} \\ &= 3.200 \cdot 8 \cdot 8 \\ &= 204.80 \text{ GBytes/s} \end{aligned}$$

For the purposes of power modelling, we either switch off Hyper-Threading (SMT on Intel® chips), or disregard it by pinning threads only on physical cores. In the same breadth, the existence of differing NUMA domain configurations on a single socket leads to variations in memory accesses, so this feature is either switched off when possible, or circumvented by choosing "balanced workloads" wherein we set the same number of threads per NUMA domain.

"icx32" node

Based on the same architecture as that of the previous node, our icx32 machine consists of a dual socket Intel Xeon "Icelake" Platinum 8358 CPU. The main memory

Property	Cascade Lake (casclakesp2)	Ice Lake (icx36)
Base Clock	2.5 GHz	2.4 GHz
Max. Turbo Clock	3.9 GHz	3.5 GHz
Cores per socket	20	36
TDP	150 W	250 W
Lithography	14 nm	10 nm
L1 cache per core	32 kB	48 kB
L2 cache per core	1 MB	1.25 MB
L3 shared cache	27.50 MB	54 MB
Memory per node	384 GiB RAM	256 GiB RAM
Peak DP performance per socket	1.60 TFlops/s	2.76 TFlops/s
Peak memory bandwidth per socket	140.78 GBytes/s	204.80 GBytes/s

TABLE 2.1: CPU metrics between our Cascade Lake and Ice Lake nodes

specifications are identical although it does have instead a slightly smaller *Lowest Level Cache (LLC)* of 48 MB. Hence the maximum theoretical bandwidth specifications follow from those of icx36.

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{\text{peak}} &= n_{\text{cores}} \cdot f_{\text{base}} \cdot I_{\text{cycle}} \cdot m_{\text{FMA}} \cdot \frac{W}{64} \\
 &= 32 \cdot 2.6 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 8 \\
 &= 2.66 \text{ TFlops/s}
 \end{aligned}$$

2.1.3 A note on frequency downscaling

On Intel chips, the frequency impact and the specific frequency transition behavior with a larger core count depends on both the width of the operation and the specific instruction used [20]. License-based downclocking refers to an effect on Intel ma-

FIGURE 2.1: Frequency downscaling with core count on a single Cascade Lake socket

FIGURE 2.2: Frequency downscaling with core count on a single Ice Lake socket

chines wherein lower than nominal frequency limits are imposed when certain SIMD

instructions are executed, especially heavy floating point instructions or 512-bit wide instructions. Interestingly, we see a reduction in the number of license levels in this new 3rd generation Xeon architecture. In contrast with Cascade Lake [2.1] which appears to have a different license for each instruction width, it appears that we now only have 2 licenses that dictate frequency. In the table below [2.2], one notices that there is no distinction of scaling in heavy workloads (which most floating point operations incur) for scalar and vectorized code. In fact, there seems to now be no distinction between heavy and light workloads as well [2.3].

Width	Light	Heavy
Scalar	L0	N/A
128	L0	L0
256	L1	L1
512	L2	L2

TABLE 2.2: Cascade Lake clock frequency licenses

Width	Light	Heavy
Scalar	L0	N/A
Scalar	L0	L1
256	L0	L1
512	L0	L1

TABLE 2.3: Ice Lake clock frequency licenses

2.2 Write-Allocate evasion on Intel machines

Modern systems employ write allocate evasion. Intel's SpecI2M is a micro-architecture feature that was introduced with the Ice Lake CPU architecture. It is a mechanism for reducing memory bandwidth demand on streaming workloads. When a CPU writes to memory, it typically first needs to read the existing contents of the cache line into the CPU cache. This is because the CPU cannot write to memory directly. This process is known as a write-allocate.

FIGURE 2.3: Memory bandwidth vs. core count on one icx36 socket for the Schöhauer Triad benchmark with Non-temporal stores and standard stores with SpecI2M on and off

For streaming workloads, where the CPU is writing large amounts of data to memory, the write-allocate process can add significant additional bandwidth traffic. SpecI2M

[24] eliminates this by allowing the CPU to allocate the cacheline to be overwritten right away in the cache hierarchy without being read from memory. This is also known as a 'Cacheline claim'. A *Non-temporal store* refers to a store policy wherein the modified data being stored is not going to be read again soon (i.e. lacks temporal locality) and so it is evicted directly to memory, bypassing the cache. This is shown in the above figure [2.3] along with our regular stores with and without SpecL2M enabled. While both non-temporal stores and Cacheline claims avoid Write-Allocate transfers, the result of a Cacheline claim is that the modified data instead resides in the cache.. From experimentation, one infers that SpecL2M is only enabled when the memory subsystem is heavily loaded. This might be to prevent SpecL2M from having a negative impact on performance for other workloads. A more thorough study of the conditions under which it works as intended and fails is given by Laukemann et al. [2023]. For the purpose of our measurements, we turn this feature off to deter the inflation of benchmarking results, and offer a more true representation of the machine's capability.

2.3 AMD machines

One of the key differences between AMD and Intel CPU design philosophies is what AMD refers to as *Core Complexes (CCX)*. In the architecture of AMD's EPYC (and Ryzen) CPUs, a CCX is a building block that contains a group of CPU cores. Each CCX typically includes a certain number of CPU cores, their associated cache (L3 cache), and sometimes other resources like memory controllers. Each core within a CCX can communicate directly with the other cores in the same CCX, which can lead to efficient data processing and reduced latency in certain applications that include sufficient LLC reuse. However, communication between cores in different CCXs have higher latencies, as it usually involves traversing a more complex path through the processor's internal fabric, commonly referred to as *Infinity Fabric* [16].

2.3.1 ZEN 3 Testsystem

Introduced in 2020, AMD's Zen 3 server processors, code-named 'Milan', were the first of the EPYC machines to utilize the 7nm+ manufacturing process. One of the fundamental changes in Zen 3 is the shift to a unified eight-core complex design. In Zen 2, each CCX had four cores, and communication between CCXs incurred a large latency penalty. This difference in layouts can be seen in the diagram below [2.4]. Zen 3 also increases the cache size directly accessible, but at the cost of a longer cycle latency [18].

FIGURE 2.4: CCX layouts comparison for Zen 2 and Zen 3

"milan1" node

The AMD EPYC 7543 is a server/workstation processor with 32 cores. It is part of the EPYC lineup, using the Zen 3 architecture with Socket SP3. Up to two EPYC 7543 CPUs can link up in a multi-processor (SMP) configuration. EPYC 7543 has a total L3 cache size of 256 MB and operates at a base frequency of 2.8 GHz by default, but can boost up to 3.7 GHz, depending on the workload. EPYC 7543 is built on a 7 nm production process using 33,200 million transistors. A point to be noted is that it supports the AVX2 standard, but not AVX-512. The peak DP performance and theoretical memory bandwidth of the CPU are

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{\text{peak}} &= n_{\text{cores}} \cdot f_{\text{base}} \cdot I_{\text{cycle}} \cdot m_{\text{FMA}} \cdot \frac{W}{64} \\
 &= 32 \cdot 2.8 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 4 \text{ TFlops/s} \\
 &= 1.43 \text{ TFlops/s}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{\text{peak}} &= f_{\text{mem}} \cdot d \cdot b_{\text{width}} \cdot N_{\text{channels}} \\
 &= 3.200 \cdot 8 \cdot 8 \text{ GBytes/s} \\
 &= 204.80 \text{ GBytes/s}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

2.3.2 ZEN 4 Testsystem

AMD's Zen 4 server processors, code-named "Genoa", are the first AMD microarchitecture to support the AVX-512 instruction set extension. Genoa processors utilize the 5nm manufacturing process, enabling a significant reduction in transistor size and power consumption. To illustrate how NPS reduces latency in memory references on a Zen 4 die, consider the diagram below. If one divides the I/O die into four quadrants for an 'NPS=4' configuration [2.5], we see that six DIMMs (Dual In-line Memory Modules) feed into three memory controllers, which are closely connected via Infinity Fabric (GMI) to a set of up to three 'Zen 4' CPU dies, or up to 24 CPU cores.

FIGURE 2.5: Dividing a 4th Gen AMD EPYC processor into four NUMA domains with NPS [14]

"genoa2" node

The genoa2 node consists of an AMD EPYC 9354, which has a base clock speed of 3.25 GHz and a turbo clock speed of 3.75 GHz. It has 64 MB of L3 cache and supports up to 6 TB of DDR5-4800 memory. It also supports up to 128 PCIe 5.0 lanes, which can be used to connect high-performance storage devices, accelerators, and other peripherals. Our DP peak performance and bandwidth numbers are as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{\text{peak}} &= n_{\text{cores}} \cdot f_{\text{base}} \cdot I_{\text{cycle}} \cdot m_{\text{FMA}} \cdot \frac{W}{64} \\
 &= 32 \cdot 3.25 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 8 \\
 &= 3.32 \text{ TFlops/s}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.4}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{\text{peak}} &= f_{\text{mem}} \cdot d \cdot b_{\text{width}} \cdot N_{\text{channels}} \\
 &= 4.800 \cdot 8 \cdot 12 \text{ GBytes/s} \\
 &= 460.80 \text{ GBytes/s}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.5}$$

Property	Milan (ZEN3)	Genoa (ZEN4)
Base Clock	2.80 GHz	3.25 GHz
Max. Turbo Clock	3.70 GHz	3.75 GHz
Cores per socket	32	32
TDP	225 W	280 W
Lithography	7 nm	5 nm
L1 cache per core	2 MiB	2 MiB
L2 cache per core	16 MiB	32 MiB
L3 cache per CCX	32 MiB	32 MiB
Memory per node	256 GiB RAM	768 GiB
Peak DP performance per socket	1.43 TFlops/s	3.32 TFlops/s
Peak memory bandwidth per socket	204.80	460.80

TABLE 2.4: CPU metrics between our chosen ZEN 3 and ZEN 4 machines

2.4 RAPL

Intel's Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) is a hardware based power and energy measurement technology introduced in the Sandy Bridge microarchitecture. It provides real-time measurements of the power consumption of the CPU package, the CPU cores, and the DRAM. Access to RAPL power data is possible via a set of dedicated *model-specific registers (MSRs)*. As the name suggests, it also includes a set of power management features that can be used to limit the power consumption of the CPU. These MSRs contain information about the power and energy consumption of the CPU. Since the ZEN architecture was first introduced, AMD machines support an MSR interface that is semi-compatible with RAPL, having the same register contents, but different actual MSR readings [33]. RAPL can measure the power consumption of the following domains on a chip:

- Package (PKG): The PKG domain measures the power consumption of the entire CPU package. This includes the CPU cores, the integrated graphics (if any), and the uncore components (last level caches, memory controller, etc.).
- Power Place 0 (PP0): THE PP0 domain measures the energy consumption of all processor cores on the socket.
- Power Plane 1 (PP1): The PP1 domain measures the power consumption of the integrated graphics (GPU) on the socket. This domain is only available on desktop and mobile CPUs.
- DRAM: The DRAM domain measures the power consumption of the random access memory (RAM) attached to the integrated memory controller.

A study by Khan et al. [2018] found that RAPL's correlation coefficient with plug power was typically around 0.95. This means that the RAPL readings were highly correlated with the actual power consumption values for most workloads.

2.4.1 LIKWID

We employ LIKWID [31], an open-source software library and suite of tools for analyzing system and application performance on a multitude of modern multicore CPUs. It provides a comprehensive set of features for measuring and profiling power consumption, energy efficiency, and other performance metrics. The energy and power metrics are derived from RAPL. The version of LIKWID used was 5.2.1

likwid-perfctr

likwid-perfctr is a versatile tool for measuring and analyzing the performance of applications and workloads on x86 processors, along with ARM, power and NVIDIA support. It provides flexible measurement options, including the ability to measure performance either as a wrapper without changing the measured application or with the Marker API, which restricts the event counting to parts of the code. likwid-perfctr also comes with a number of pre-configured performance groups with useful event sets and derived metrics, making it easy to get started with performance measurement. In addition, likwid-perfctr allows users to create their own custom event sets, giving them the flexibility to measure the specific events that are relevant to their application or workload. For example, running a job for energy and power metrics on icx36 as below.

```
1 $likwid-perfctr -m -O -c S0:0-35 -g ENERGY ./a.out
```

Here, the `-m` flag denotes marker mode which allows one to restrict the performance measurements to specific code regions, `-O` for a parse-able CSV format and `-c` allows one to select processor IDs to be measured. In this example we benchmark registers with physical cores IDs from 0-35, or 36 of the physical cores of icx36 with the assumption that the code takes care of thread pinning itself. Alternatively, a capital `-C` flag allows for thread pinning as well. Generally a plethora of options for benchmark "groups" exist that allow for the measurement of various quantities of interest. We list out a few that we use in the following chapters.

Group Name	Description
ENERGY	Information on Energy and Power dissipation of the chip and DRAM. Also provides Temperature readings per core.
CLOCK	Clock frequency of every core, as well as the uncore of the chip.
FLOPS_DP	SCALAR, AVX and AVX512 performance numbers in the form of flop throughput.
L2	Data volume through the L2 cache, for loads as well as evictions.
L2CACHE	Request rate for the L2 cache, as well as miss rates and ratios.
L3	Data volume through the L3 cache, for loads as well as evictions.
MEM	Main memory volume and bandwidth through the DRAM.

TABLE 2.5: Metrics supported by LIKWID on Ice Lake machines

When running multiple benchmarks in a single job script into a text file, it is often useful to filter out measurement results using bash scripts, such as one presented in appendix [A].

likwid-bench

likwid-bench is a lightweight microbenchmarking tool that allows users to measure and compare the performance of streaming kernels on x86, as well as ARM and POWER processors. It is built on top of the likwid-perfctr library and provides a number of pre-defined assembly kernels for common applications and workloads, such as CPU and memory benchmarks. likwid-bench also allows users to create their own custom benchmarks. The assembly boilerplate for memory registers and marker labels are taken care of automatically. We employ these assembly benchmarks since a compiler could otherwise interfere with the nature of micro-benchmarking. Additionally, by listing the amount of flops, bytes, instructions and uops in a loop, we are also provided with predictions for many performance metrics such as flop throughput and bandwidth. This may also act as a first test for validity when performing measurements. For example, to run an assembly daxpy subroutine, one may invoke

```
$likwid-bench -t daxpy -i 100 -w S0:4GB:36:1:2
```

The `-w` flag indicates the workgroup placement of the kernel, alternatively with capital `-W` that allows a thread to initialize its own data in accordance with the *First Touch* policy. The First Touch policy in *ccNUMA* (*cache-coherent Non-Uniform Memory Access*) refers to a memory allocation strategy used in multi-processor systems where the memory is not uniformly accessible to all processors. In a ccNUMA architecture, processors or cores may access their own local memory faster than non-local memory (memory local to other processors). Under the First Touch Policy, memory is allocated on the node where the accessing thread or process is executing at the time of the first memory access. This means when a processor first accesses a previously unallocated page of memory, that page is allocated on the memory node closest to that processor. This policy is designed to improve memory

access times by ensuring that memory is as close as possible to the processor using it thereby reducing latency. The `-i` flag denotes the iteration count, if omitted, `likwid-bench` chooses an iteration size as to let the benchmark run for a few seconds. The placement argument includes colon separated parameters, which here are, the memory domain, workload size, thread count, thread block size, and displacement stride respectively. For systems with SMT on, one may choose a displacement of 2 as above to only consider physical cores on the socket. In the above example, we choose to place 36 threads on the S0 domain, with a block size of one processor per thread, and a displacement of 2 to bypass SMT. For sockets with SNC on, there are additionally options for choosing a specific NUMA domain.

```
1 STREAMS 2
2 TYPE DOUBLE
3 FLOPS 2
4 BYTES 24
5 DESC Double-precision linear combination of two vectors, only
   scalar operations
6 LOADS 2
7 STORES 1
8 INSTR_CONST 17
9 INSTR_LOOP 19
10 UOPS 26
```

LISTING 2.1: Typical `likwid-bench` header

2.5 Reproducibility

When considering benchmarking, a key consideration is reproducibility. In the accompanied Jupyter notebooks, while every benchmark already has its core frequency and uncore clock recorded, we also use *MachineState* [14] for further documentation. This open source tool can be run before benchmarks are made, allowing one to document system configurations of interest at a given point and overall a code's execution environment in a JSON-like file format. While we do not include these system state files for every benchmark, we do attach them for important strategic microbenchmarks. We have used *MachineState* version 0.4.1 for the provided data which may be accessed [here](#).

Chapter 3

Microbenchmarks, Code Characteristics and Performance

A microbenchmark is a type of benchmark test that focuses on measuring the performance of a very small and specific piece of code. Unlike broader benchmark tests that evaluate the performance of entire systems or large applications, microbenchmarks focus in on particular functions or operations to understand their behavior in great detail. This level of granularity allow for the analysis of specific low level intructions. Regarding code characteristics, we consider two classes of loop streaming kernels- compute bound, or *scalable* code, and memory bound, or *saturating* code. We refrain from discussing I/O (Input/Output) bound code since our interest primarily relies on the CPU chip rather than networks or disk usage.

3.1 Code Characteristics

3.1.1 Scalable, compute bound code

Compute bound code is that which is limited by the performance of processing units on a machine. This type of code is typically characterized by a high ratio of floating-point operations (FLOPs) to memory accesses, or a low *Cycles Per Instruction (CPI)* ratio.

```

1  .align 32
2  LOOP 1
3  movsd    FPR2, [STR0 + GPR1 * 8 ] #Load from memory
4  addsd    FPR1, FPR2
5  addsd    FPR3, FPR4
6  mulsd    FPR5, FPR6
7  mulsd    FPR7, FPR8
8  mulsd    FPR9, FPR10
9  addsd    FPR11, FPR12
10 addsd    FPR13, FPR14
11 mulsd    FPR15, FPR16
12 addsd    FPR1, FPR2
13 addsd    FPR3, FPR4
14 mulsd    FPR5, FPR6
15 mulsd    FPR7, FPR8
16 mulsd    FPR9, FPR10
17 addsd    FPR11, FPR12
18 addsd    FPR13, FPR14
19 mulsd    FPR15, FPR16

```

LISTING 3.1: Code snippet of Peakflops, which involves multiple flops and a single byte load for x86 machines

When code is compute bound, the hardware generally spends more time executing instructions than it is waiting for data from memory. Typical examples in scientific computing include matrix multiplication and force calculation kernels in molecular dynamics (MD) codes.

Metric	Peakflops scalar	DGEMM scalar
Core Power	203.37 W	204.78 W
DRAM Power	16.83 W	8.42 W
Performance	150.36 GFlop/s	131.13 GFlop/s
Bandwidth	75.39 GBytes/s	52.98 GBytes/s
CPI	0.45 cy/l	0.72 cy/l
Operational Intensity	2.0 Flops/Byte	87.85 Flops/Byte

TABLE 3.1: Benchmarked measurements using an entire Ice Lake socket with selected scalable codes

Since we are primarily interested in micro-benchmarking, we primarily consider loops as shown above [3.1], which consider multiple floating point instructions such as ADDs and MULTs with different vector register widths, and relatively few loads or stores. As we will see later [3.6], the existence of heavy, powerful instructions such as FMAs and AVX-512 push the required operational intensity required for loop kernels to be compute bound. As a result, for the purpose of micro-benchmarking, we often take out the LOAD instruction from these assembly loops to ensure scalability. This can be validated with a plot of performance throughput over active core count, such the one pictured below [3.1].

FIGURE 3.1: Scalability of Peakflops and DGEMM across cores on Ice Lake with fixed clock speeds of 2.2 GHz

While considering C++ kernels, we consider the *Double-precision General Matrix Multiply (DGEMM)* algorithm which calculates the product of two dense matrices

$$C(i, j) = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \cdot A(i, k) \cdot B(k, j)$$

where n is the inner dimension matrix size, $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $A, C \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. Scalar and vectorized variants are provided in Appendix [B]. We use C++ intrinsics to create AVX2 and AVX512 variants. Intrinsics in C++ refer to a set of special function-like commands that allow developers to directly use processor-specific instructions without needing to write assembly code. They are designed to map directly to machine instructions, typically offering more efficient and direct control over hardware capabilities than what is possible through standard C++ code. Highest performance was found to be achieved through the usage of both intrinsics as well as performant compiler flags.

3.1.2 Saturating, memory bound code

Saturating, memory bound code is code that is limited by the memory bandwidth of the system. This type of code is typically characterized by a high ratio of memory accesses to CPU instructions and a low CPI as a result.

```

1  .align 32
2  LOOP 1
3  movsd   FPR1, [STR1 + GPR1*8] # Load from stream 1
4  movsd   FPR2, [STR1 + GPR1*8+8]
5  movsd   FPR3, [STR1 + GPR1*8+16]
6  movsd   FPR4, [STR1 + GPR1*8+24]
7  mulsd   FPR1, [STR2 + GPR1*8]
8  addsd   FPR1, [STR3 + GPR1*8]
9  mulsd   FPR2, [STR2 + GPR1*8+8]
10 addsd   FPR2, [STR3 + GPR1*8+8]
11 mulsd   FPR3, [STR2 + GPR1*8+16]
12 addsd   FPR3, [STR3 + GPR1*8+16]
13 mulsd   FPR4, [STR2 + GPR1*8+24]
14 addsd   FPR4, [STR3 + GPR1*8+24]
15 movsd   [STR0 + GPR1*8], FPR1 # Store with stream 4
16 movsd   [STR0 + GPR1*8+8], FPR2
17 movsd   [STR0 + GPR1*8+16], FPR3
18 movsd   [STR0 + GPR1*8+24], FPR4

```

LISTING 3.2: Code snippet involving the scalar Schöhauer triad for x86 machines

When code is memory bound, the CPU spends more time waiting for data from memory than it spends executing instructions. While CPUs have become significantly faster in recent years, the performance gap between CPUs and memory access has widened. This has led to a trend of codes becoming more memory bound.

Metric	Triad scalar	CG scalar
Core Power	189.95 W	236.95 W
DRAM Power	25.78 W	23.9065 W
Performance	9.26 GFlops/s	42.04 GFlops/s
Bandwidth	154.78 GBytes/s	176.18 GBytes/s
CPI	3.82 cy/l	1.01 cy/l
Operational Intensity	0.06 Flops/Byte	0.24 Flops/Byte

TABLE 3.2: Benchmarked measurements using an entire Ice Lake socket with selecting saturating codes

FIGURE 3.2: Saturation of Schönauer Triad and Conjugate Gradient benchmarks across cores on Ice Lake with fixed clock speeds of 2.2 GHz

Above, we consider the Schönauer triad which calculates in every inner loop

$$a(i) = b(i) \cdot c(i) + d(i)$$

for $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{R}^n$. We then have a load to store ratio of 3:1, and an operational intensity of $2/32 = 0.0625$ flops/byte, which should be clearly memory bound on modern machines. For C++ kernels, we consider the conjugate gradient linear system solver, with an *Operational Intensity (OI)* of 0.25 flops/byte. For very sparse matrices, the CG method can be compute-bound because the operations involve fewer memory accesses. The sparser the matrix, the less data needs to be loaded into memory. For simplicity, we consider the dense matrix version, which is also easier for the compiler to vectorize. The scalar version is listed in Appendix [B]. The AVX version is obtained during compilation with appropriate flags. It may be noted that our CG code saturates the memory bandwidth at a much later point over active cores as compared to the vector triad benchmark [3.2]. This is expected due to the lower operational intensity of the code, and may also be predicted through a roofline plot as introduced below.

3.2 The roofline model

The roofline model is a performance model used to estimate the performance of applications on multi-core and many-core architectures. The term was first coined by Williams [2009] in his doctoral thesis *"Auto-tuning Performance on Multicore Computers"*. Initially developed as a performance analysis tool, it has evolved to encompass power efficiency considerations. It was originally introduced to assess the performance of computational kernels by plotting performance against hardware limitations. It employs a graph that resembles a roofline, with the Y-axis representing computational performance and the X-axis indicating operational intensity (the ratio of computational operations to data movement). This graphical representation helps identify bottlenecks and understand the potential for improvement within a

given hardware and software context. When extending the Roofline Model to consider power consumption, it becomes a powerful tool for evaluating the energy efficiency of algorithms and applications. The model allows one to distinguish between computation-bound and memory-bound code, providing insights into how efficiently an application utilizes available hardware resources.

FIGURE 3.3: A roofline plot with multiple ceilings (Molina et al. [2022])

As such, the defining characteristics of a system can be drawn from

- **Performance Roof:** This represents the theoretical performance limits of the hardware. It is typically an upper boundary on the graph and is often based on the peak performance of the CPU or GPU. The performance roof can be calculated in terms of FLOPS (Floating-Point Operations Per Second) or some other relevant performance metric.
- **Operational Intensity:** Operational intensity refers to the ratio of computational work (e.g., FLOPs) to data movement (e.g., memory accesses). It is a measure of how efficiently an algorithm utilizes the hardware. Operational intensity is plotted on the x-axis.

One may populate the graph using experimentally achieved data points. These are actual performance and operational intensity measurements taken from running a specific algorithm or application on the hardware. These data points represent the achieved performance at various operational intensities. The model helps identify performance bottlenecks. If the data points are far below the roofline, it suggests that the application may be limited by memory bandwidth, latency, or other hardware constraints. This insight is crucial for pinpointing areas for optimization. The roofline model can also be used to compare different algorithms and choose the one that best matches the hardware's capabilities.

3.2.1 The roofline model applied to our test systems

Here we apply the model to our Cascade Lake system on an entire socket. Our data points are obtained by starting with a peakflops code, and altering its operational intensity [3.4]. One notices for such a graph that the power draw is highest

FIGURE 3.4: Ice Lake Roofline for a fixed Core and Uncore clock of 2.2 GHz

FIGURE 3.5: Ice Lake Power Draw over Operational Intensity variations

closest to the knee. This is the point at which the bandwidth limited performance meets the compute throughput roof. This is because the benchmark engages both, a considerable chunk of the memory bandwidth, as well as the full chip. For our Ice Lake node, we see that with our roofs drawn for vectorized instructions with FMAs, even the provided likwid-bench kernel is insufficient to reach peak performance in our measurements. Although one may simply increase the operational intensity to circumvent this, we find no obvious consequence to forgoing the LOAD entirely. This means that our compute bound metrics are now cacheline transfer free, and may be used in isolation to determine other characteristic CPU instructions as seen here [3.6]. Of course, for a given kernel, the Operational Intensity remains the same, where as the performance may vary with vectorized instructions or through using fused multiply add instructions. An initial conclusion can be drawn for memory bound

FIGURE 3.6: Ice Lake roofline with assembly kernels at fixed clock speeds

FIGURE 3.7: Genoa roofline with assembly kernels at fixed clock speeds

code. In the above figures, the STREAM benchmark has close to the exact performance using either scalar or vectorized instructions. This indicates that for heavily memory bound code, that is, points on the far left of a roofline diagram, that SIMD vectorization presents no quantitative advantage. In fact, if one were to consider the

fact that power dissipation would then be higher for roughly the same runtime, it would instead be a detriment in energy efficiency.

Chapter 4

Power trends

We begin with preliminary examinations of energy dissipation behaviour. As a start, we investigate energy dissipation over active cores, and then while simultaneously considering performance, here measured via flop throughput. It may be noted that one of the primary factors contributing to energy dissipation in server CPUs is the switching activity of their transistors. Transistors consume energy when they switch between their on and off states, and the higher the frequency of switching, the greater the energy consumption. To reduce switching activity, server CPUs employ various techniques, such as out-of-order execution, speculative execution, and *dynamic voltage and frequency scaling (DVFS)*. To avoid these fluctuations, we investigate only 'steady state' loops, which are phases during benchmarking where the system's performance metrics reach a stable, consistent state. This includes having fixed core as well as uncore clock in every benchmark considered.

4.1 Energy to solution

4.1.1 General trends

Race to idle/Race to sleep refers to a concept in computing where the goal is to complete a given task as quickly as possible and then return the system to an idle state. The rationale is that a processor consumes less energy when idle, so minimizing active processing time can reduce overall energy consumption. This concept is particularly relevant in scenarios where the code is compute-bound and scalability is a key consideration.

FIGURE 4.1: Compute bound energy dissipation curve over active core

FIGURE 4.2: Memory bound energy dissipation curve over active cores

Since we know beforehand [3.1] that our peakflops benchmark is scalable across cores, it comes as no surprise that the lowest Energy to solution is observed while engaging the entire socket. To illustrate the vast energy difference while using vector registers, we use a log plot [4.1]. Since we expect a baseline power consumption due to the sheer fact that activated transistors draw current, we observe a Race to an idle state for any configuration of instruction set width and frequency for scalable code. Next for memory bound code, it's expected that we arrive at an operating point wherein we saturate the main memory bandwidth. At and beyond this point, adding cores will only result in a stagnation, or even reduction in energy dissipation. Since we're considering large memory sizes (of the order of $\sim 4\text{GBytes}$) in our measurements, we are streaming data from main memory and hence data locality is not surveyed. In the above example benchmark [4.2], one can observe an energy saving of roughly 20% between the marked data points wherein we use half the chip socket and scalar instructions over using vectorized instructions with the whole socket. Of course, energy cost is just one facet of a HPC system. Since many scientific algorithms are built on the premise of speed, one should simultaneously consider performance.

4.1.2 Energy-Delay products

As the domain's name suggests, speed is crucial in High Performance Computing systems. In fact, the most common benchmark used to rank HPC systems is *Highly Parallel Linpack (HPL)*, which concerns itself with the solution of dense linear equation systems, which as one can expect, employ very compute bound linear algebra routines [19]. Hence we now consider both energy dissipation, as well as performance in terms of FLOP throughput. An intuitive way to understand their interplay is by simply plotting energy dissipation for the solution of a fixed size workload to it's performance.

FIGURE 4.3: Z-plot for compute bound code on Ice Lake with two fixed clock speeds and vectorized instructions

We refer to this diagram as a *Z-plot* [23] in the following text. In such a plot, horizontal lines depict constant energy dissipation, and vertical lines depict a constant flop throughput. To populate such a curve, one may either consider a fixed frequency clock while varying the active cores, or vice versa. Because we consider a fixed problem size, our chosen performance metric then is inversely proportional to runtime, or *delay*. A straight line through the origin then has a units of [Js], and so it is directly proportional to the *Energy Delay Product (EDP)* of a code. This is a critical metric for evaluating the efficiency and performance trade-offs in processor design and operation. As a composite measure it provides a more holistic view of a CPU's performance than considering either metric alone. This concept is particularly important in the era of energy-conscious computing, since it captures the trade off between maximizing performance while minimizing energy consumption is key. For illustration, two points along a curve in a plot may have a the same energy to solution, but a point further along the x-axis will have better performance. This characterises it's energy delay product and is a good metric for favorable configurations since the energy remains the same, but the code runs faster, which is obviously preferable. In the Ice Lake Z plots, we set the core clock equal to the uncore. For scalable code, here the peakflops benchmark with AVX512 instructions [4.3], the lowest observed EDP coincides with the lowest energy to solutions. This ties back in with the "Race to Idle" behaviour of such a code characteristic.

FIGURE 4.4: Z-plot for memory bound code on Ice Lake at three fixed clock speeds with points of minimum EDP marked with dashed lines

As expected, the general wisdom is to run the code with as many cores activated, with the highest clock available for the best operational configuration. For saturated code, portrayed here with our scalar triad benchmark [4.4], we once again see a characteristic change in behaviour of performance once the memory hierarchy is saturated. At a point along the curve, the performance stagnates, or even degrades while we have a higher energy dissipation overall due to more engaged cores. By multiplying our maximum observed main memory bandwidth by the kernel's operational intensity, we would arrive at a roofline prediction of performance.

Hence we expect a flop throughput of $172.4/16 = 10.7$ GFflops, which is what is observed above [4.4].

FIGURE 4.5: Triad Z-plot on Cascade Lake with lines of minimum EDP at fixed clock speeds

FIGURE 4.6: Triad Z-plot over frequency on Ice Lake for a set of fixed active core counts

While the inflection point now displays a considerably smaller performance and energy efficiency degradation than seen in previous architectures such as Sandy Bridge (Hofmann et al. [2018]), the behaviour persists, and it appears that an ideal operating scenario with lowest EDP still involves a certain number of active cores at a reduced frequency [4.4]. On the other hand, choosing clock speed as our variable parameter over a fixed core count allows us to hit memory saturation earlier, and thus see this inflection point more clearly as graphed above [4.6]. Our Cascade Lake machine still shows a larger turn around despite the smaller socket size of just 20 cores [4.5]. For our AMD machines, since these chips do not allow for Uncore frequency selection, we can only set the Core clock. As a result we don't observe the same characteristic behaviour as seen in Intel chips.

FIGURE 4.7: Genoa Z-plot using peak-flops at two fixed core and uncore clock frequencies

FIGURE 4.8: Genoa Z-plot using the Schönauer triad at two fixed core and uncore clock frequencies

4.2 Power model

Here we attempt to test and validate our assumed power model (1.7). This model was formulated for previous architectures, wherein the Uncore clock was not a configurable parameter. As a result, it was assumed that it follows the set Core clock speed. Hence, the following subsections will consist of benchmarks with the Uncore clock configured to be the same as the core frequency. The benchmarks are primarily performed on our Intel machines since in addition to not having a configurable/measurable Uncore frequency, the AMD Zen machines also only have three settable clock speeds apart from turbo. For reference, on Cascade Lake the base frequency is 2.5 GHz, which is also the maximum settable uncore clock speed. On Ice Lake the base frequency is 2.4 GHz, but the uncore has a maximum of frequency of 2.2 GHz, limiting the number of data points we have. To ensure a meaningful benchmark environment, none of the measurements presented below are with turbo enabled.

4.2.1 Polynomial power model

To begin, we use the assumption that the Core power only depends on the Core frequency and scales linearly with the number of active cores. For the assumed Baseline power, we could then write

$$P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{Uncore}}) = P_{\text{chip}} - n \cdot P_{\text{core}}(f_{\text{Core}}, n)$$

The power of the chip can be measured using the Package Power domain using LIKWID. Next we may consider either a scalable code kernel, or a saturating code kernel upto a core count point wherein the chip power still scales linearly. This is to eliminate the core count dependence in $P_{\text{core}}(f_{\text{Core}}, n)$ seen in kernels that do not have a parallel efficiency of 1. This allows us to then extrapolate a linear approximation in package power over active cores, which lets us arrive at a Baseline power described by the plot's y-intercept. We may further populate such a plot for different fixed clock speeds.

FIGURE 4.9: Extrapolation to zero cores on Cascade Lake using peakflops and the Schönhauer triad at two clock speeds

FIGURE 4.10: Extrapolation to zero cores on Ice Lake using peakflops and the Schönhauer triad at two clock speeds

Fortunately, we still see that independent of code characteristics, our extrapolation to zero cores for a fixed core and uncore clock still yields roughly the same y-intercept value. This acts as a first validation to our modelling assumptions of a Baseline Power that is kernel independent. As one would expect, the behaviour of Baseline Power in frequency is monotonically increasing. This estimation of static power dissipation is quite large as compared to previous architectures. For reference, a clock speed of 2.0 GHz has an estimate for 45 W in our Cascade Lake machine, and of the magnitude of over double for Ice Lake with 93 W. Comparatively, Sandy Bridge had a value of less 25 W. Moreover, since the Sandy Bridge chip used had only a TDP of 135 W, the static power draw was roughly just a fifth of the total possible power dissipation. Cascade Lake and Ice Lake have TDPs of 150 W and 250 W respectively. This results in a much larger of comparative power draw of about a third and over of the total.

4.2.2 Fitting and validation

We may now use these intercepts previously as our static power dissipation. This allows us to fit the previous mentioned polynomial (1.5) of baseline power over uncore frequency using the same data

$$P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{Uncore}}) = W_0^{\text{base}} + W_1^{\text{base}} \cdot f_{\text{Uncore}} + W_2^{\text{base}} \cdot f_{\text{Uncore}}^2$$

FIGURE 4.11: Static power variation at different fixed core and uncore clock speeds on Cascade Lake

FIGURE 4.12: Quadratic Baseline Power fit on Cascade Lake using the peak-flops benchmark

While the quadratic fits are numerically not bad, with a small magnitudes of residue of 0.612 and 0.703 for the Cascade and Ice Lake least squares problems respectively, the magnitude of the negative linear co-efficient, and comparatively small quadratic coefficient present a divergence in the behaviour previously seen in Sandy Bridge. Nevertheless, these values cannot be taken with physicality in mind, as it is reinstated that they are only fit parameters. To illustrate, in the quadratic fits shown above [4.12,4.14], an extrapolation of the polynomial towards low frequencies shows an uncharacteristic behaviour towards to assumed model. Next we attempt to determine behaviour for our in-core power by approximating the in-core power dissipation as

$$P_{\text{core}}(f_{\text{Core}}, n) = (P_{\text{chip}} - P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{Uncore}})) / n$$

FIGURE 4.13: Static power variation at different fixed core and uncore clock speeds on Ice Lake

FIGURE 4.14: Quadratic Baseline Power fit on Ice Lake using the peakflops benchmark

Using these values, we then fit the polynomial core power model over clock frequency (1.6).

$$P_{\text{core}}(f, n) = (W_0^{\text{core}} + W_1^{\text{core}} \cdot f_{\text{core}} + W_2^{\text{core}} \cdot f_{\text{core}}^2) \epsilon(n)^\alpha$$

Consider peakflops measurements, for scalable code, having a parallel efficiency of $\epsilon = 1$.

FIGURE 4.15: Derived per-core power on Ice Lake using the peakflops benchmark

FIGURE 4.16: Derived per-core power on Genoa using the peakflops benchmark

The larger quadratic coefficient suggests a more convincing polynomial behaviour, but now we have a negative constant static per-core term. For Genoa, the power dissipation of the Core and L3 memory can be measured separately directly from the MSRs. This allows us to fit a measured per-core power cost and compare numbers to our derived values. Both are of the order of a few Watts per core without using turbo. Furthermore, the fact that the curve data points for the Genoa machine lie directly on top of each other gives merit to the idea that linear in-core power draw varies linearly over active core counts.

Finally, the previous paper had predicted an optimal operating frequency was as stated here (1.8). For our Ice Lake machine (icx36), we would then have from the above fits, the function

$$f_{\text{opt}} = \sqrt{\frac{103.15 + n \cdot (-0.16)}{27.94 + n \cdot 0.51}}$$

Next, using the vector triad benchmark once again, we may mark true optimal frequencies over our previous Z-plot [4.6] for fixed core counts. What may be problematic, is that now, although small, our constant coefficient for the core fit is negative.

Cores	f_{opt}	True f_{opt}
8	1.78 GHz	1.7 GHz
16	1.66 GHz	1.8 GHz
24	1.57 GHz	1.7 GHz
32	1.48 GHz	1.5 GHz

FIGURE 4.17: Calculated and true optimal frequencies

FIGURE 4.18: True optimal frequencies over Z-plots [4.6]

Oddly enough, the true optimal frequency does not appear to be a strictly decreasing function. This could be due to the fact that we now have the ability to directly set the Uncore frequency, and it is not just assumed to be equal to the Core clock as previously experimented. Surprisingly, the predictions do not seem to be far off [4.17]. This could be due to the fact that the baseline power constant co-efficient is just very large, and thus it primarily determines the optimal values.

4.3 DRAM model

Here we seek to quantify DRAM power. On Intel machines, LIKWID measures DRAM power as a separate measure-able domain. We choose micro-benchmarks that focus on memory traffic to and from main memory. Starting with LOAD only code, we plot DRAM power dissipation over main memory bandwidth. The behaviour does indeed seem to be roughly linear in nature, with an independence from the actual Uncore frequency set [4.19]. We then assume the linear behaviour

$$P_{\text{DRAM}} = \theta_0 + \theta_1 \beta$$

FIGURE 4.19: DRAM power varied over core count with 1 stream

FIGURE 4.20: DRAM power varied over core count with 4 streams

where β is the main memory bandwidth, and θ_0, θ_1 are fit parameters from the plots. It appears that having more streams for a given code kernel does increase both the intercept and the slope of the linear fit, with an observable jump from one to two load streams [4.21], but ultimately these variances are too small for consideration in the context of an actual DRAM model. Similarly, with a fixed number of data streams,

FIGURE 4.21: Variation over number of streams

FIGURE 4.22: Variation over STORE/LOAD ratio

and a variation in the the ratio of LOADs to STOREs [4.22], as one would expect, we observe a higher power draw for STORE operations. It should be mentioned that the plots are made with non-temporal STORE instructions, for a more 'fair' assessment. Even though we are not using write-allocates in our code, the eviction of cachelines to main memory should still, and clearly does, result in an increase in bandwidth traffic.

Chapter 5

Parameterized power costs

In this section, we attempt to construct systematic approaches to micro-benchmark elementary operations on the CPU. The goal would be to allow one to parameterize the cost associated to a given instruction empirically. While we have seen that the baseline power is quite large in modern systems, in the context of assembly kernels the optimization of low-level instructions directly influences overall system performance as well. An understanding of the power costs associated should then assist in estimating the energy consumption of a generic code. Various studies have contributed to the understanding of power and energy costs in different computational scenarios. For instance, Vasilakis [2015] conducted a comprehensive analysis of power consumption at the instruction level, shedding light on the nuances of energy-efficient programming practices. Their work highlighted the significance of considering not only execution time but also the power implications of specific ARM instructions. The results of the investigation below categorizes the energy consumption of a CPU into in-core contributions and those which arise from the memory hierarchy in the form of static power and cacheline transfer costs.

5.1 Memory hierarchy

5.1.1 Uncore baseline power

As before [4.9], we employ our power model assumptions to arrive at the cost of the static 'baseline' power for our chip. A caveat to be noted, is that we cannot completely isolate the static power dissipation of a chip as a consequence of only the uncore parts of the CPU die. For example, if one benchmarks assembly loops with no actual in-core flop calculations such as a load or store only code, one still observes a variation in derived baseline power for different core clock frequencies. This suggests that this baseline static power exists for not only the memory hierarchy, but the core as well.

5.1.2 Cacheline transfer energy

To evaluate the cost associated with an individual cache line across our memory hierarchy, a systematic novel approach is employed. We initiate the benchmark with a deliberately slow in-core code, such as a floating point division or square root operation loop, accompanied by a singular data load operation. An imperative step is to ensure an instruction dependency chain by reusing the same processor registers, which not only enables a lower flop throughput, but also a cooler chip core due to fewer hardware sections being utilized. Having a core with a lower power dissipation should make variations in the energy consumption due to cacheline transfers in the

memory hierarchy easier to observe. Using an iterative strategy over workload sizes, we begin with an in-register memory placement, and then progressively increase the data sizes while proportionally reducing the iteration count, so as to keep flop count the same. This ensures that the CPU cores do exactly the same amount of work, with a relatively low variation (<1%) in performance, due to the slow flop throughput and relatively quick cache transfers. All the while ensuring the ability to place data in different levels of the cache and memory hierarchy. The job script can be viewed in Appendix [A].

```

1  .align 32
2  LOOP 1
3  movsd    xmm1, [STR0 + GPR1 * 8]
4  sqrtsd   xmm1, xmm2    #Instruction dependency
5  sqrtsd   xmm1, xmm2
6  sqrtsd   xmm1, xmm2
7  sqrtsd   xmm1, xmm2
8  sqrtsd   xmm1, xmm2
9  sqrtsd   xmm1, xmm2
10 sqrtsd   xmm1, xmm2
11 sqrtsd   xmm1, xmm2

```

LISTING 5.1: Slow compute-bound SQRT instructions with a dependency chain and a single load

The objective is to then discern the difference in energy to solution, while attributing the additional energy consumption due to new lower cache levels of the chip being utilized. To do this, we normalize the energy discrepancy by the number of transferred cache lines to obtain an estimate for the additional energy consumption per cache line across the entire system.

FIGURE 5.1: Energy dissipation over memory placement on Ice Lake using the dependency chain SQRT kernel with fixed uncore and core clock speeds

Understandably, this approach introduces noticeable noise for L1-L2 energy cost estimation. Nevertheless, we observe a noticeable point from which the data exceeds the L1 cache size is contained entirely within the inclusive L2 cache, and then an increase through the lowest level L3 cache, until we finally hit the memory plateau and see saturation once again [5.1]. It is easy to see that these jumps in energy costs align with those at the same memory sizes in plots of main memory traffic and DRAM energy costs as well [5.2,5.3].

FIGURE 5.2: Main memory bandwidth over memory placement on Ice Lake using the SQRT kernel

FIGURE 5.3: DRAM energy dissipation on Ice Lake using the SQRT kernel at a fixed clock speed

The result of this experiment would suggest that sending a single cacheline from main memory to the L2 cache would cost 41.03 nJ including DRAM energy contributions [5.1]. As a comparison, Choi et al. [2013] had estimated a value of 795 pJ/Byte, or 50.88 nJ for a single cacheline transfer on an Intel Bloomsfield machine using an integrated power measurement device.

Measured region	Energy cost
Core	31.39 nJ/cacheline
DRAM	9.64 nJ/cacheline
Core + DRAM	41.03 nJ/cacheline

TABLE 5.1: Ice Lake cacheline transfer cost estimates

One can similarly perform estimations on Cascade Lake and Genoa. Cascade lake shows a similar value of 27.98 nJ for a cacheline, while Genoa seems to show about half as much. While cascade lake shows a plateau at an understandably lower memory size due to smaller caches at every level, the Genoa machine only seems to plateau at much larger values. For example, it appears to be at about 2 GB here [5.5]. This can be attributed to the core chip design on Zen 4 machines. The estimation for Cascade Lake seems to be in line with that of Ice Lake, while for Genoa the value appears to be half as much. This could be attributed to the memory hierarchy of AMD ZEN chips. The modular chiplet design in ZEN4 might contribute to more efficient memory access patterns, potentially reducing energy usage. The L3 cache, is quite a bit larger in Zen chips, which is crucial for reducing the frequency of main

FIGURE 5.4: Energy dissipation over memory placement on Cascade Lake using the dependency chain SQRT kernel

FIGURE 5.5: Energy dissipation over memory placement on Genoa using the dependency chain SQRT kernel

memory accesses, possibly leading to the lower energy consumption that we see here [5.5].

Architecture	Energy cost
Cascade Lake	27.98 nJ/cacheline
Genoa L3	11.88 nJ/cacheline
Genoa core	1.74 nJ/cacheline
Genoa core + L3	13.63 nJ/cacheline

TABLE 5.2: Cascade Lake and Genoa cacheline transfer cost estimates

5.2 Floating point operation costs

Estimating the cost of an elementary floating point operation is not a trivial task. One sees that even within the same characteristic benchmark, usage of different registers and order of operations makes a sizeable difference. For this reason, it would be desirable to use other known quantities to quantify these costs better. An approach that seems to work well is to consider in-core power dissipation using flop throughput over CPU cycle count. The behaviour of assumed core power, here derived by subtracting baseline power from package power, seems to clearly depend linearly on this flop throughput [5.6]. This allows for one to then estimate a baseline core power for the chip, and assess the power consumption of more calculation heavy workloads by extrapolating along this fit. Here one then has

$$P_{\text{core}} = P_{\text{static}}(f_{\text{core}}) + \mu \cdot P_{\text{dynamic}}(f_{\text{core}}) \quad (5.1)$$

where μ is the flop throughput, P_{core} is the fit intercept which depends on the clock frequency, and P_{dynamic} is the dynamic coefficient which is determined from the fit's slope.

FIGURE 5.6: Derived in-core power over flop throughput at a selection of different clock frequencies with a fixed uncore speed

While one would expect a larger static power with a higher clock, it's interesting to note that the slope of the fit also increases with frequency. This seems to be less apparent in Ice Lake [5.6] and more noticeable in Cascade lake [5.9], where the slope can effectively double without using turbo clock speeds.

FIGURE 5.7: Instruction width effect on core power dissipation on Ice Lake

FIGURE 5.8: FMA effect on core power dissipation on Ice Lake

Of course, one seems that for wider register widths a larger 'baseline' core power is suggested, but also a significantly lower increase while obtaining a larger throughput. This suggests a behaviour in which vectorized instructions draw a larger initial power, but pay off in energy costs for more core demanding workloads.

FIGURE 5.9: Core power dissipation on Cascade Lake

FIGURE 5.10: Instruction width effect on Cascade Lake core power dissipation

This ties into the general trends seen earlier, in which streaming benchmarks which are heavily memory bound seem to suffer in energy efficiency while using this vectorized instructions. The case with FMAs seems to follow a like minded path. The assumed baseline stays constant for a given clock frequency and instruction width, but these Fused Multiply Adds have roughly half the dynamic power as can be seen from the slope coefficients [5.8].

5.3 Grey box energy estimations

A grey box model in CPU power modeling represents a method that combines elements from both black box and white box models to predict or analyze the power consumption of a CPU (Central Processing Unit). Since for baseline power, our estimation comes from an independent variable (f_{uncore}) with a fixed function fit, the same being for cacheline energy estimations as well, we consider this a white box approach. Our microbenchmarks for core power as a function of operating frequency and flop throughput, on the other hand, only constitute observable input-output values and can be thought of as a black box method. Hence we consider the following a grey-box, or hybrid approach. We use certain known characteristics of the CPU's architecture and combine this with empirical data about its performance and power consumption under different conditions.

5.3.1 Naive model

Using the previous parameterized energy and power draw costs in this chapter, we seek to estimate the energy of a code kernel using a greybox approach. We consider the following preliminary model for energy consumption

$$E = (P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{uncore}}) + P_{\text{core}}(f_{\text{core}})) \cdot t + \epsilon \cdot n_{\text{mem}}$$

where t is runtime, P_{base} is our initially fitted quadratic polynomial through our extrapolation to zero, P_{core} [5.1] follows from our register flop throughput benchmarks, n_{mem} is the number of cachelines transfered to and from main memory, and ϵ is the

approximated energy for each said cacheline.

For Cascade Lake, we use our previous polynomial fit [4.12], and our ϵ parameter of 27.98 nJ/CL. Since we were unable to ascertain a function over clock frequencies and instruction widths for our observed static and dynamic core powers, we list them for different instruction widths and two chosen operating frequencies below. The naive model will then use these values for energy estimations.

P_{core}	f = 1.6 GHz	f = 2.2 GHz
SCALAR static	19.72 W	28.33 W
SCALAR dynamic	5.11 W μ^{-1}	8.51 W μ^{-1}
AVX static	21.51 W	31.27 W
AVX dynamic	1.74 W μ^{-1}	2.03 W μ^{-1}
AVX512 static	22.27 W	31.73 W
AVX512 dynamic	3.11 W μ^{-1}	4.01 W μ^{-1}

TABLE 5.3: Cascade Lake core power parameters for different instruction widths over two fixed clock speeds

For Ice Lake, one again we consider our quadratic polynomial [4.14] for our static baseline power. Our previously determined data transfer estimate of 31.39 nJ for a cacheline from main memory [5.1] will be used for our ϵ parameter.

P_{core}	f = 1.6 GHz	f = 2.2 GHz
SCALAR static	17.11 W	39.82 W
SCALAR dynamic	16.92 W μ^{-1}	16.42 W μ^{-1}
AVX static	18.01 W	40.04 W
AVX dynamic	3.18 W μ^{-1}	4.97 W μ^{-1}
AVX512 static	15.87 W	45.63 W
AVX512 dynamic	2.13 W μ^{-1}	3.31 W μ^{-1}

TABLE 5.4: Ice Lake core power parameters for different instruction widths over two fixed clock speeds

5.3.2 Testing and validation

We begin by making estimations on our assembly benchmarks. We used peakflops to estimate in-core power dissipation, so it comes to no surprise that our energy estimations fall very close to true values. These estimates are within an error of about 1% – 2%, and seem to agree for different combinations of core and uncore frequencies, as well as for both our Ice Lake and Cascade Lake nodes. Meanwhile, it is observed that for any other memory bound kernels, that we have an underestimation of between 5% – 10%. This may be attributed for the lack of consideration of parallel efficiency while measuring in core power dissipation. It’s clear that to achieve the same flop throughput for a memory bound code, one needs to utilize much more computational resources as compared to scalable code. Since we expect power saturation as a function of flop throughput, it makes sense that we over-estimate our power draws. To rectify this, a possible method would be a type of scaling parameter based on the parallel efficiency of a given kernel. This would be quite tedious

to perform for every benchmark, so for our naive computations, we forego such an endeavour.

FIGURE 5.11: Peakflops grey-box estimations on Ice Lake over two clock frequencies

FIGURE 5.12: Schön-hauer triad grey-box estimations on Ice Lake over two clock frequencies

On the other hand, we see that for our C++ kernels, we underestimate by very large margins, of upto 20% – 25% in some cases. Since both the conjugate gradient and DGEMM algorithms incorporate cache reuse, our negligence of intercache transfers is likely a leading cause of this naive model’s estimations. For the Conjugate gradient method, if the involved matrices are sparse and well-structured, the CG method might exhibit a more streamlined access pattern where data can be efficiently fetched from memory. However, irregular memory access patterns can occur depending on the sparsity and structure of the matrix. The amount of cache utilization and inter-cache transfers can vary. For large systems where the matrices and vectors do not fit into cache, you might see more direct streaming from memory. However, for smaller systems or parts of the computation that fit into cache, there could be effective use of the cache, reducing the need for frequent memory accesses.

FIGURE 5.13: Peakflops grey-box estimations on Cascade Lake over two clock frequencies

FIGURE 5.14: Schön-hauer triad grey-box estimations on Cascade Lake over two clock frequencies

FIGURE 5.15: C++ kernel power estimations on Ice Lake over two clock frequencies and using different instruction widths

For DGEMM, the data transfer between different levels of cache and memory is usually significant, especially for large matrices that exceed the cache size. However, these transfers are usually optimized to reduce cache misses and make effective use of the memory hierarchy. Modern implementations of DGEMM (like those in optimized libraries such as Intel's MKL or OpenBLAS) are heavily optimized for cache usage. They typically employ techniques like blocking and tiling to ensure that a maximal amount of data reuse occurs within the cache levels, minimizing memory bandwidth requirements. Since we're using a simple implementation without much manual optimization, this discrepancy is understandable and expected. The fact that the lowest level cache on these machines is not inclusive, lends to the difficulty of determining costs of inter-cache transfers. Using a statistical regression model might overcome this issue, as is presented in the following chapter.

Chapter 6

Statistical power model

In this final section, we introduce an alternative approach to power dissipation estimates by leveraging the statistical prowess of regression. Regression analysis allows one to model the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables, provides a framework for this endeavor. The approach begins with the collection of data under various operational scenarios. Given the complex, multifaceted nature of power dissipation, this dataset will serve as the foundational element of our model. It incorporates a range of variables, including core and uncore clock speeds, the number of active cores, cache level bandwidth, flop throughput, and instruction throughput. To refine our analysis, we employ feature reduction techniques to identify and utilize only the most significant measurements. This process leads to the formulation of a validated model. The final stage involves testing our model against previously un-encountered code kernels. These tests are conducted using both assembly and C++ benchmarks, providing a comprehensive evaluation of the model’s applicability and accuracy in realistic scenarios.

6.1 Model Data

We select a number of streaming loop assembly kernels from likwid-bench. Here we list the number of loads, stores, operational intensity (OI) and UOPs in every iteration of the code loop. We then benchmark over a variety of core and uncore clock frequencies, active cores and memory sizes.

Benchmark	LOADS	STORES	OI	UOPS
Triad	3	1	0.0625	30
Stream	2	1	0.0833	26
Peakflops	1	0	2.0000	19
Dot product	2	0	0.1250	18
Daxpy	2	1	0.0833	26
Load	1	0	0.0000	10
Copy	1	1	0.0000	14

TABLE 6.1: Training data benchmarks

Lastly we set up our feature variables with quantities of interest such as performance metrics, unhalted cycles, L2 & L3 cache transfers and retired instruction counts.

6.2 The Gauss-Newton Method

The Gauss-Newton method is an iterative optimization algorithm widely used to solve nonlinear least squares problems. These problems arise in various fields, such as statistics and optimization, where the objective is to minimize the sum of the squares of the differences between observed and predicted values.

6.2.1 Target Variable

Consider a general form of a nonlinear least squares problem involving an objective function $f(x)$, representing the sum of squared differences between observed data y_i and predicted values $\hat{y}_i(x)$:

$$\min_x f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i - \hat{y}_i(x)]^2 \quad (6.1)$$

The Gauss-Newton method starts with an initial guess for the parameter vector x . At each iteration, it updates the parameter vector to minimize the objective function. The key idea is to linearize the objective function around the current parameter estimate. This linearization is achieved by using the first-order Taylor expansion:

$$\hat{y}_i(x) \approx \hat{y}_i(x_k) + J_i \Delta x \quad (6.2)$$

where J_i is the Jacobian matrix evaluated at the current estimate x_k , and Δx is the change in the parameter vector. The Gauss-Newton update rule is derived by setting the gradient of the linearized objective function to zero:

$$J^T J \Delta x = -J^T f(x_k) \quad (6.3)$$

where J^T is the transpose of the Jacobian matrix, and $f(x_k)$ is the vector of residuals. The update to the parameter vector is then given by $x_{k+1} = x_k + \Delta x$. The algorithm continues iterating until a convergence criterion is met to a local minima.

6.2.2 Model Formulation

After trial and evaluation, we consider the following model to be fitted as our target variable. Note that since we consider power as our target feature, we normalize our L2 and L3 cacheline counts by time. While the notion of an additional power draw for a higher cacheline count per second might initially seem odd, the normalization with runtime does provides a unit of watts/bandwidth. We have earlier seen that DRAM power can be modelled with regards to main memory bandwidth, so this concession could be interpreted as having a physical meaning with power dissipation as a function of cache bandwidth as well.

$$P = P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{uncore}}) + n \cdot P_{\text{core}}(f_{\text{core}}) + \beta_0 \cdot L2 + \beta_1 \cdot L3 + \gamma \cdot I \quad (6.4)$$

where $L2$ and $L3$ represent the respective time normalized cachelines, or in other terms, cache bandwidths. This means that the coefficients β_0, β_1 are now fitted parameters with units of watts/bandwidth for the respective cache levels. Here I

represents the total number of retired instructions normalized once again by time and γ is its respective fit coefficient. Finally, as before we use the previous polynomial assumptions for base and core power

$$P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{uncore}}) = W_0^{\text{base}} + W_1^{\text{base}} \cdot f_{\text{uncore}} + W_2^{\text{base}} \cdot f_{\text{uncore}}^2 \quad (6.5)$$

and

$$P_{\text{core}}(f_{\text{core}}) = W_0^{\text{core}} + W_1^{\text{core}} \cdot f_{\text{core}} + W_2^{\text{core}} \cdot f_{\text{core}}^2 \quad (6.6)$$

6.3 Trained model and results

Below we present our fitted parameters and benchmark results for our two Intel architectures. Regrettably, in addition to main memory bandwidth measurements being unreliable on our Zen machines, the cache group performance counters of likwid-perfctr also do not provide information on cacheline evictions. As a result the assumed model would be too data deficient, and is hence omitted.

6.3.1 Cascade Lake

We employ Scipy's *least_squares* module to create and solve our least squares system by providing functions for the model and residual. The following data is obtained for our Cascade Lake machine. The fitted parameters in general appear to agree with previous findings. For example, both quadratic power polynomials have a large negative term as seen before and have their minima past their origin values.

Fitted coefficient	Power cost
W_0^{base}	65.65 W
W_1^{base}	$-45.21 \text{ W}[\text{GHz}]^{-1}$
W_2^{base}	$17.65 \text{ W}[\text{GHz}]^{-2}$
W_0^{core}	1.94 W
W_1^{core}	$-1.85 \text{ W}[\text{GHz}]^{-1}$
W_2^{core}	$0.76 \text{ W}[\text{GHz}]^{-2}$
β_0	$13.62 \text{ nWCL}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
β_1	$4.37 \text{ nWCL}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
γ	$0.14 \text{ nWI}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$

TABLE 6.2: Cascade Lake fitted regression parameters using the aforementioned benchmark data

To get a feel for the quantitative consequences, let's make a few comparisons to our assumed estimations from previous chapters. Starting with uncore base power for an uncore clock of 2.0 GHz, a quick calculation would give us an estimate of 45.83 Watts. Through our previous extrapolation to zero cores [4.11], we had approximated a value of 43.72 Watts, which seems to be in agreement. In case of data transfers, we had previously estimated a value of 27.98 nJ [5.2] for a single cacheline transferred from main memory to a core's L2 cache. We can now consider a benchmark's energy contribution from cache transfers in the following way: Approximate energy required for a data transfer through the cache hierarchy by our β coefficients. Next we can divide this estimate by the total number of cachelines transferred, since

we know the number of data bytes loaded and evicted from our assembly kernels. For illustration, performing this on a dot product benchmark from likwid-bench, a value of 23.29 nJ/CL is calculated. Once again, within the order of our previous manual estimation. Here in [6.1], we present the estimations and true costs of two

FIGURE 6.1: Cascade Lake power draw estimations on selected assembly and C++ benchmarks using a full socket

unseen likwid-bench kernels, as well as two of our C++ benchmarks from previous chapters. We see that withing an error margin of about 5%, we're able to estimate package power dissipation. It is to be noted that the level of optimization and compiler flags used does effect the accuracy of this estimation by a large amount. In general, we see better accuracy with high optimization and using highly performant compile options. One may notice that the error is highest for the compute bound DGEMM kernel. When we benchmark for core power parameters, we do not include a code's parallel efficiency. This means that our tabulated results represent a 'average' over such a parameter. The benchmarks we had used for our model data are primarily memory bound code kernels, which understandably would cause such a behaviour. Nevertheless, we omit such a fit parameter, since this would then require multiple runs of a unseen loop kernel to estimate its parallel efficiency.

6.3.2 Ice Lake

Next for Ice Lake, we use the same optimization strategy for our fitted parameters as below [6.3]. Once again, let's try to make sense of these values. For an uncore clock of 2.0 GHz, we then estimate an uncore power dissipation of 93.36 W [4.13]. Once again, this value comes in very close to our estimation of 96.43 W . Next, we use the same cache energy method as before to achieve a value of 28.11 nJ/CL . Once again, not too far off from our estimated energy per cacheline of 31.39 nJ/CL as seen in [5.1]. As before, the error is in the margin of 5% for tested benchmarks. A point to be noted is the accuracy of the model seems to depend on optimization flags made when compiling. Better optimized code appears to fit more in line to actual power measurements.

Fitted coefficient	Energy cost
W_0^{base}	141.22 W
W_1^{base}	$-108.15 \text{ W}[\text{GHz}]^{-1}$
W_2^{base}	$42.11 \text{ W}[\text{GHz}]^{-2}$
W_0^{core}	2.51 W
W_1^{core}	$-3.08 \text{ W}[\text{GHz}]^{-1}$
W_2^{core}	$1.11 \text{ W}[\text{GHz}]^{-2}$
β_0	$11.17 \text{ nWCL}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$
β_1	$1.65 \text{ nWCL}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$
γ	$0.17 \text{ nWI}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$

TABLE 6.3: Ice Lake fitted regression parameters using the aforementioned benchmark data

FIGURE 6.2: Ice Lake power draw estimations on selected assembly and C++ benchmarks using a full socket

6.4 Stencil codes

6.4.1 1D 3 point stencil

The Jacobi method, a staple in numerical analysis, is widely used for solving systems of linear equations, particularly those arising from discretized partial differential equations (PDEs). The 3-point Jacobi stencil is a specialized, simplified version of this method, tailored for one-dimensional problems. In the 3-point stencil approach, each point in a discrete spatial domain is updated based on its current value and the values of its immediate neighbors. This method is derived from the broader concept of stencils in numerical analysis, where a stencil defines the set of array elements used to compute a given element. For a linear array of points x , the 3-point Jacobi stencil updates each point x_i using the formula:

$$x_i^{\text{new}} = 0.3334 * (x_{i-1}^{\text{old}} + x_i^{\text{old}} + x_{i+1}^{\text{old}})$$

Since for such a stencil code we can calculate a priori the cache data transfers, we attempt to estimate the power dissipation. If we have an array of 10 million doubles, and consider 100 iterations, the problem set size will be

$$\begin{aligned} N &= 2 \cdot 10^7 \cdot 10^2 \cdot 8 \text{ Bytes} \\ &= 1.6 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ Bytes} \\ &= 2.5 \cdot 10^8 \text{ CLs} \end{aligned}$$

Since we have write allocates, this mean we will have $2N$ cachelines loaded through the L2 cache, and N cachelines evicted. Since L3 functions as an exclusive victim cache, we then have $2N$ cachelines both loaded and evicted from/to memory. We may also estimate the number of retired instructions by calculating

$$\begin{aligned} |I| &= N_{\text{flops}} + N_{\text{bytes}} \\ &= 1.9 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ Instructions} \end{aligned}$$

Now, we assume that the performance may me estimated through an analytical model to give us runtime. We then have the evaluation for a set core and uncore clock of 1.6GHz, with a single threaded run

$$\begin{aligned} P &= P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{uncore}}) + n \cdot P_{\text{core}}(f_{\text{core}}) + \beta_0 \cdot L2 + \beta_1 \cdot L3 + \gamma \cdot I \\ &= 38.50 + 0.92 + 2.61 + 1.11 + 1.86 \\ &= 45.03 \text{ Watts} \end{aligned}$$

and for a set core and uncore clock of 2.2GHz

$$\begin{aligned} P &= P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{uncore}}) + n \cdot P_{\text{core}}(f_{\text{core}}) + \beta_0 \cdot L2 + \beta_1 \cdot L3 + \gamma \cdot I \\ &= 51.62 + 1.55 + 3.16 + 1.35 + 1.86 \\ &= 59.56 \text{ Watts} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we may calculate values using the Ice Lake fitted parameters. For a set core and uncore clock of 1.6GHz, with a single threaded run, we then have

$$\begin{aligned} P &= P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{uncore}}) + n \cdot P_{\text{core}}(f_{\text{core}}) + \beta_0 \cdot L2 + \beta_1 \cdot L3 + \gamma \cdot I \\ &= 76.00 + 0.42 + 2.65 + 0.52 + 1.07 \\ &= 80.68 \text{ Watts} \end{aligned}$$

and for a set core and uncore clock of 2.2GHz

$$\begin{aligned} P &= P_{\text{base}}(f_{\text{uncore}}) + n \cdot P_{\text{core}}(f_{\text{core}}) + \beta_0 \cdot L2 + \beta_1 \cdot L3 + \gamma \cdot |I| \\ &= 107.14 + 1.10 + 3.33 + 0.65 + 1.34 \\ &= 113.59 \text{ Watts} \end{aligned}$$

We are now able to compare our estimations using both the regressional model and a-propri calculations, as well as our true measured values from likwid-perfctr [6.3,6.4]. The results look promising, with a relative error once again of between 2 – 3%.

FIGURE 6.3: A-priori calculation comparisons on Cascade Lake for the 3 point stencil on a single core

FIGURE 6.4: A-priori calculation comparisons on Ice Lake for the 3 point stencil on a single core

6.4.2 2D 5 point stencil

The 5-point Jacobi stencil is an extension of the basic Jacobi iterative method, primarily used for solving two-dimensional partial differential equations (PDEs). This method is pivotal in numerical analysis and computational science, especially for grid-based computations in physics, engineering, and related fields. The 5-point stencil uses a simple yet effective approach to approximate solutions to PDEs, making it invaluable in both academic and practical applications. The 5-point stencil

operates on a two-dimensional grid. For a point in the grid with coordinates (i, j) , the stencil updates the point's value based on its current value and the values of its four immediate neighbors (left, right, up, down). The update formula is typically as follows:

$$x_{i,j}^{\text{new}} = 0.25 * (x_{i-1,j}^{\text{old}} + x_{i+1,j}^{\text{old}} + x_{i,j-1}^{\text{old}} + x_{i,j+1}^{\text{old}})$$

Over a 2D grid, a sweep over lattice point using a Jacobi smoother would then give us

```

1 for (int i = 1; i < rows - 1; ++i) {
2     for (int j = 1; j < cols - 1; ++j) {
3         new_grid[i][j] = 0.25 * (grid[i-1][j] + grid[i
4 +1][j] + grid[i][j-1] + grid[i][j+1]);
5     }
}

```

LISTING 6.1: Sweep over lattice points with the Jacobi smoother

For such a loop kernel, we would have a write-allocate for *new_grid*, and well as 3 reads for the old grid with indices $(i+1, j)$, $(i-1, j)$, $(i, j+1)$. The lattice point with index will still be available in the cache since it was read two updates prior. This is because in C++, multidimensional arrays are stored in the row-major order, which stores consecutive elements in rows in contiguous memory addresses. This results in a naive balance of 5 Words for a *Lattice Site Update (LUP)*, or 40 Bytes with double precision vectors. Consider an grid with dimensions of 10^2 rows and 10^7 columns. Considering a sweep performed with a single iteration then gives us a main memory traffic size of

$$\begin{aligned}
 N &= 5 \cdot 10^9 \cdot 8 \text{ Bytes} \\
 &= 4.0 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ Bytes} \\
 &= 6.25 \cdot 10^8 \text{ CLs}
 \end{aligned}$$

This also gives us the data traffic through the L2 cache. Due to the victim cache behaviour of the L3, we will then have 4 reads and 4 evictions. We would then have the data traffic for the L3 as

$$\begin{aligned}
 N &= 64 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Bytes} \\
 &= 10.0 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ CLs}
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, to estimate the total number of retired instructions, we have 4 bytes of data for every flop which gives us

$$\begin{aligned}
 |I| &= N_{\text{flops}} + N_{\text{bytes}} \\
 &= 8 \cdot 10^9 + 2 \cdot 10^9 \\
 &= 1.0 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ Instructions}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6.7}$$

We may now use these values to produce the same calculations as previously done for the three point stencil. This allows us to once again compare our estimations with actual measurements and a-priori calculations, as shown in [6.5].

FIGURE 6.5: A-priori calculation comparisons on Cascade Lake for the 5 point stencil on a single core

FIGURE 6.6: A-priori calculation comparisons on Ice Lake for the 5 point stencil on a single core

Cache blocked variant

Cache blocking, also known as loop blocking or loop tiling, is an effective optimization technique in high-performance computing, especially in the context of iterative methods such as the 5-point Jacobi stencil. This technique is designed to enhance data locality and reduce cache misses, thereby improving the overall computational efficiency. Cache blocking involves restructuring the computation to process data in small blocks or tiles that fit into the cache. By doing so, it reduces the number of times data must be loaded from the slower main memory, leveraging the faster cache memory more effectively. Without cache blocking, each iteration over the grid may lead to significant cache misses, as the data accessed may not be in close proximity in memory. We implement this using the following idea.

- **Divide the Grid into Blocks:** The entire grid is divided into smaller, rectangular blocks or tiles. The size of these blocks is chosen based on the cache size to ensure that a block's data fits into the cache.
- **Nested Loops for better data access:** The implementation uses two sets of nested loops: the outer loops iterate over the blocks, and the inner loops iterate over the elements within each block.

This may be achieved in our code, by tiling the column dimension with a given block size. To choose an appropriate block size, we consider how many elements would fit into our L2 cache such that we may hold 3 grid layers over a block sweep. This would require $32 \cdot n_{\text{cols}}$ elements to be stored [25]. To illustrate such a calculation, consider our Ice Lake machine has a cache size of 1.25 MBytes per core. With a safety margin of half the cache size, we would have

$$\begin{aligned} N_{\text{block}} &= \frac{0.5 \cdot 1250 \cdot 1024}{32} \text{ elements} \\ &= 20,000 \text{ elements} \end{aligned}$$

This means we'd like to have 20,000 elements in our inner most loop. In the code snippet below [6.2], we now have a loop over the blocks, while we may parallelize with an openMP directive over the row iterations.

```

1 for (int bj = 1; bj < cols - 1; bj +=block){
2     int jMax = std::min(bj + block, cols - 1);
3     #pragma omp parallel for
4     for (int i = 1; i < rows - 1; ++i) {
5         for (int j = bj; j < jMax; ++j) {
6             new_grid[i][j] = 0.25 * (grid[i-1][j] +
7             grid[i+1][j] + grid[i][j-1] + grid[i][j+1]);
8         }
9     }

```

LISTING 6.2: Sweep over lattice points with the Jacobi smoother

Since the cache is blocked to hold 3 rows of the grid, we now have once again a write-allocate for *new_grid*, and just one read for the lattice point with index $(i + 1, j)$. Hence three out of five of our cache hits come from the L2, and we now only have a main memory balance of only 24 Bytes for a LUP using DP vectors. Of course, our L2 data traffic should still have a size of 40 Bytes, but now the L3 will now only have two loads and two evictions, resulting in $4 \cdot 8 = 32$ Bytes for every lattice site update. Once again, we present the approximations using the regressional model with measured and calculated data traffic sizes and instruction counts [6.7]. The actual power

FIGURE 6.7: A-priori calculation comparisons on Cascade Lake for the cache blocked variant of the 5 point stencil

FIGURE 6.8: A-priori calculation comparisons on Ice Lake for the cache blocked variant of the 5 point stencil

measurements are slightly lower as compared to the naive implementation, but one does see an increase in the relative error. This may be attributed to the fact that now, the L2 memory data traffic differs from that of the main memory traffic. Since our model does not currently use the main memory bandwidth as a approximation parameter, this could be the cause of the increase in power estimation. Nevertheless, the kernels still show a total error of less than 5% for both the measured input and a-priori calculations.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

We have ventured into a comprehensive exploration of power consumption within modern server grade CPUs, a subject that holds increasing significance in the era of escalating energy demands and environmental concerns. Using microbenchmarks encompassing different code characteristics, we were able to scrutinize and validate power models of previous generations on current high performance x86 hardware. To begin with, we observed familiar behavioural trends in energy dissipation across an increasing number of active cores for a fixed clock speed. As one would expect, scalable code still presents a Race-to-idle situation whereas highly saturating code shows a reduction in energy dissipation after a certain point which worsens with vectorization. While graphing Z-plots, a noticeable characteristic difference in Ice Lake machines was observed. The inflection point, at which we see a lower performance as well as a reduction in energy efficiency, is not as drastic as in for previous generations, but seems to now to suffer less while engaging more cores. Next, the power model we had assumed, seems to quantitatively still fit well, but a with changes that do not accurately reflect a quadratic polynomial behaviour in frequency. Nevertheless, our domain of frequency study is not large enough that this qualitative change affects our fits too badly. In addition, we were able to quantify DRAM power dissipation with a simple linear behaviour in memory bandwidth, in which uncore and core clock frequencies seem to play no influence. In addition, an increase in baseline DRAM power was seen for a larger data stream count.

The thesis further sheds light on the parameterized power costs associated with elementary operations, uncovering the intricate techniques involved in estimating these costs. Through a strategic microbenchmarking we were able to assume the cost of transferring a cacheline of data from main memory into a core's L2 cache for different CPU architectures. We had also witnessed the multifaceted nature of in-core power draw wherein it is influenced by multiple factors, including core clock frequency, the utilization of vectorized instructions, and the existence of accumulative operations, such as Fused Multiply Adds. This fact suggests that a fixed energy dissipation for an instruction would be an inconsistent value across different workloads, and instead a more nuanced method would be considering flop throughput, which can be estimated for a given workload, assuming that performance models exists that can predict the number of cycles said workload requires. Using these parameterized instruction costs, we were then able to construct a naive preliminary power model using a grey-box approach. While this approach worked quite well for benchmarks that were scalable in cores, an overestimation was found for saturating cores, wherein the model does not account for a reduction in per core power for achieving the same throughput. In addition, we saw the effects of neglecting intercache data considerations through a gross underestimation of C++ kernels with actual cache reuse, as seen with our DGEMM and CG examples. This beckoned an approach both with a new metric in core power, as well for cache traffic. Lastly, we refined our model using

a regressional approach with nonlinear least squares. Through feature reduction we arrived at a model that incorporates variables such as core and uncore frequency, inter-cache data transfer costs, and retired instruction throughput. We were then able to quantify power dissipation in unseen assembly benchmark codes within an error of 1 – 2% and unknown C++ codes with a maximum error of 5%. In addition, for algorithms for which one can explicitly calculate cache data traffic, such as those exemplified with our stencil codes, one may calculate a-priori the number of cachelines transferred through the L2 and L3 caches, allowing in conjunction with an approximation for retired instructions, an estimate without actually performing measurements on a code. This is of course still with the assumption that other performance models allow for the calculation of runtime in cycles. An improvement that could be made is the inclusion of code specific fit parameters, such as parallel efficiency.

As we look ahead, the findings of this thesis hold interesting implications for the future of HPC system design and optimization. The intricate interplay between code characteristics, microarchitectural features, and power consumption necessitates a nuanced approach to developing energy-efficient computing strategies. Future research directions could encompass the exploration of emerging technologies such as heterogeneous computing. Another idea would be to not only target steady state loops, but those which involve processors in different p-states.

Appendix A

Bash scripts

A.1 GREP script to extract measurements

```
1 #!/bin/bash
2
3 # Check if the file name was provided as an argument
4 if [ -z "$1" ]; then
5     echo "Usage: $0 <file>"
6     exit 1
7 fi
8
9 # Check if the file exists
10 if [ ! -f "$1" ]; then
11     echo "File does not exist."
12     exit 1
13 fi
14
15 # Find all lines containing the phrase 'Power [W] STAT'
16 lines=$(grep "Power \[W\]," "$1")
17
18 # Check if any lines were found
19 if [ -z "$lines" ]; then
20     echo "Phrase 'Power [W] STAT' not found."
21     exit 1
22 fi
23
24 # Extract the value between the first and second comma on each
25 # line and join them with commas
26 values=$(echo "$lines" | cut -d ',' -f 2 | paste -sd ",")
27
28 # Print the values
29 echo "$values"
```

LISTING A.1: GREP script example

A.2 SLURM job script for cacheline transfer estimates

```
1 #!/bin/bash
2 #SBATCH -N 1
3 #SBATCH --ntasks=1
4 #SBATCH --time=09:00:00
5 #SBATCH -C hwperf
6 #SBATCH --nodelist=casclakesp2
```

```
7 #SBATCH --cpus-per-task=80
8 . /etc/profile
9
10 module load likwid/5.2.1
11 #srun likwid-setFrequencies --umin 2.0 --umax 2.0
12 HOSTNAME=$(hostname | cut -d '.' -f 1)
13 srun likwid-setFrequencies -t 0
14 srun likwid-setFrequencies --min 2.2 --max 2.2
15 srun likwid-setFrequencies --umin 2.2 --umax 2.2
16
17 for i in {1..44}
18 do
19     mem=1000
20     iter=2000000
21     mem=$(echo "$mem * 1.2^$i" | bc)
22     mem=$(printf "%.0f" "$mem")
23     iter=$(echo "$iter/(1.2^$i)" | bc)
24     iter=$(printf "%.0f" "$iter")
25     #echo "$mem" >> output.txt
26     #echo "$iter" >> output.txt
27     #srun likwid-setFrequencies --umin $i --umax $i
28     #srun likwid-setFrequencies --min $i --max $i
29     srun --cpus-per-task=80 --cpu-freq=2200000-2200000:
performance likwid-perfctr -m -O -c S0:0-19 -g ENERGY likwid
-bench -t divmore -i $iter -W S0:${mem}K>done
```

LISTING A.2: SLURM job queuing example

Appendix B

Code

B.1 Conjugate gradient

```
1 #include <iostream>
2 #include <vector>
3 #include <cmath>
4 #include <omp.h>
5 #include <likwid.h>
6
7 // Simple vector class
8 class Vector {
9 public:
10     std::vector<double> data;
11
12     Vector(int size) : data(size, 0.0) {}
13
14     int size() const {
15         return static_cast<int>(data.size());
16     }
17
18     double& operator[](int index) {
19         return data[index];
20     }
21
22     const double& operator[](int index) const {
23         return data[index];
24     }
25 };
26
27 void applyOperator(const Vector& x, Vector& result) {
28     int size = x.size();
29     #pragma omp parallel for
30     for (int i = 0; i < size; ++i) {
31         result[i] = 2.0 * x[i]; // Example: Diagonal matrix
32         // with 2 on the diagonal
33     }
34 }
35
36 // Conjugate Gradient solver
37 void conjugateGradient(const Vector& b, Vector& x, int
38     maxIterations, double tolerance) {
39     int size = b.size();
40
41     Vector r(size), p(size), Ap(size);
```

```
41 // Initialize
42 double alpha, beta, rsold;
43
44 // r = b - Ax
45 applyOperator(x, Ap);
46 #pragma omp parallel for
47 for (int i = 0; i < size; ++i) {
48     r[i] = b[i] - Ap[i];
49     p[i] = r[i];
50 }
51
52 rsold = 0.0;
53 #pragma omp parallel for reduction(+:rsold)
54 for (int i = 0; i < size; ++i) {
55     rsold += r[i] * r[i];
56 }
57
58 // Main iteration loop
59 for (int iter = 0; iter < maxIterations; ++iter) {
60     // Ap = A * p
61     applyOperator(p, Ap);
62
63     // alpha = rsold / (p * Ap)
64     double pAp = 0.0;
65     #pragma omp parallel for reduction(+:pAp)
66     for (int i = 0; i < size; ++i) {
67         pAp += p[i] * Ap[i];
68     }
69     alpha = rsold / pAp;
70
71     // x = x + alpha * p
72     #pragma omp parallel for
73     for (int i = 0; i < size; ++i) {
74         x[i] += alpha * p[i];
75     }
76
77     // r = r - alpha * Ap
78     #pragma omp parallel for
79     for (int i = 0; i < size; ++i) {
80         r[i] -= alpha * Ap[i];
81     }
82
83     // beta = (r * r) / rsold
84     double rsnew = 0.0;
85     #pragma omp parallel for reduction(+:rsnew)
86     for (int i = 0; i < size; ++i) {
87         rsnew += r[i] * r[i];
88     }
89     beta = rsnew / rsold;
90
91     // p = r + beta * p
92     #pragma omp parallel for
93     for (int i = 0; i < size; ++i) {
94         p[i] = r[i] + beta * p[i];
95     }
96
97     rsold = rsnew;
```

```
98     }
99 }
100
101 int main() {
102     // LIKWID initialization
103     LIKWID_MARKER_INIT;
104     #pragma omp parallel
105     {
106         LIKWID_MARKER_THREADINIT;
107         LIKWID_MARKER_REGISTER("CG");
108     }
109     const int size = 1000000;
110     const int maxIterations = 1000;
111     const double tolerance = 1e-16;
112
113     Vector b(size), x(size);
114
115     #pragma omp parallel
116     {
117         // LIKWID marker start
118         LIKWID_MARKER_START("CG");
119         // Conjugate Gradient solver
120         conjugateGradient(b, x, maxIterations, tolerance);
121         // LIKWID marker stop
122         LIKWID_MARKER_STOP("CG");
123     }
124     // Output the result or perform further computations
125
126     // LIKWID finalize
127     LIKWID_MARKER_CLOSE;
128
129     return 0;
130 }
```

LISTING B.1: SCALAR Conjugate Gradient benchmark

B.2 Double precision Matrix Multiplication

```

1 #include <immintrin.h>
2 #include <stdio.h>
3 #include <stdlib.h>
4 #include <string.h>
5 #include <likwid.h>
6 #define N 15000
7
8 void dgemm_avx512_omp(double *A, double *B, double *C) {
9     #pragma omp for
10    for (int i = 0; i < N; i += 8) {
11        for (int j = 0; j < N; j += 8) {
12            __m512d c[8][8];
13            // Initialize c to zero
14            for (int ii = 0; ii < 8; ++ii) {
15                for (int jj = 0; jj < 8; ++jj) {
16                    c[ii][jj] = _mm512_setzero_pd();
17                }
18            }
19
20            // Perform matrix multiplication using AVX-512
21            for (int k = 0; k < N; k += 8) {
22                for (int ii = 0; ii < 8; ++ii) {
23                    for (int jj = 0; jj < 8; ++jj) {
24                        __m512d a = _mm512_loadu_pd(&A[(i + ii)
25 * N + k]);
26                        __m512d b = _mm512_loadu_pd(&B[k * N + (
27 j + jj)]);
28                        c[ii][jj] = _mm512_fmadd_pd(a, b, c[ii][
29 jj]);
30                    }
31                }
32            }
33
34            // Store the results in C
35            for (int ii = 0; ii < 8; ++ii) {
36                for (int jj = 0; jj < 8; ++jj) {
37                    _mm512_storeu_pd(&C[(i + ii) * N + (j + jj)
38 ], c[ii][jj]);
39                }
40            }
41        }
42    }
43
44    int main() {
45        double *A, *B, *C;
46        A = (double *)malloc(N * N * sizeof(double));
47        B = (double *)malloc(N * N * sizeof(double));
48        C = (double *)malloc(N * N * sizeof(double));
49        LIKWID_MARKER_INIT;
50        #pragma omp parallel
51        {
52            LIKWID_MARKER_THREADINIT;
53            LIKWID_MARKER_REGISTER("DGEMM");
54        }
55    }

```

```

52 // Initialize matrices A and B with random values
53 for (int i = 0; i < N * N; ++i) {
54     A[i] = (double)rand() / RAND_MAX;
55     B[i] = (double)rand() / RAND_MAX;
56 }
57 #pragma omp parallel
58 {
59     LIKWID_MARKER_START("DGEMM");
60 // Solve the system using the conjugate gradient method
61 dgemm_avx512_omp(A, B, C);
62 LIKWID_MARKER_STOP("DGEMM");
63 }
64 LIKWID_MARKER_CLOSE;
65
66 // Free allocated memory
67 free(A);
68 free(B);
69 free(C);
70
71 return 0;
72 }

```

LISTING B.2: DGEMM AVX512 variant

B.3 Three point stencil with Jacobi Iterations

```

1 #include <iostream>
2 #include <vector>
3 #include <random>
4 #include <omp.h>
5 #include <likwid.h>
6
7 void jacobi_3pt_stencil(std::vector<double>& values, std::vector
<double>& new_values, int iterations, int n) {
8     for (int it = 0; it < iterations; ++it) {
9         #pragma omp parallel for
10        for (int i = 1; i < n - 1; ++i) {
11            new_values[i] = (values[i - 1] + values[i] + values[
i + 1]) * 0.3334;
12        }
13
14        #pragma omp parallel for
15        for (int i = 1; i < n - 1; ++i) {
16            values[i] = new_values[i];
17        }
18    }
19 }
20
21 int main() {
22     const int size = 10000000; // Large array size
23     const int iterations = 100; // Number of iterations
24     omp_set_num_threads(1);
25     LIKWID_MARKER_INIT;
26     #pragma omp parallel
27     {

```

```

28     LIKWID_MARKER_THREADINIT;
29     LIKWID_MARKER_REGISTER("threepoint");
30 }
31 // Initialize random number generator
32 std::random_device rd;
33 std::mt19937 gen(rd());
34 std::uniform_real_distribution<> dis(0.0, 1.0);
35
36 // Initialize array with random values between 0 and 1
37 std::vector<double> values(size);
38 for (double& value : values) {
39     value = dis(gen);
40     //value = 0.0;
41 }
42 int n = values.size();
43 std::vector<double> new_values(n);
44 #pragma omp parallel
45 {
46     // LIKWID marker start
47     LIKWID_MARKER_START("threepoint");
48     jacobi_3pt_stencil(values, new_values, iterations, n);
49     LIKWID_MARKER_STOP("threepoint");
50 }
51 LIKWID_MARKER_CLOSE;
52 return 0;
53 }

```

LISTING B.3: Jacobi smoothing with the three point stencil on a 1D grid

B.4 Cache blocked five point stencil with Jacobi Iterations

```

1 #include <iostream>
2 #include <vector>
3 #include <cstdlib>
4 #include <random>
5 #include <cmath>
6 #include <algorithm>
7 #include <likwid.h>
8 #include <omp.h>
9
10 void jacobi_5pt_stencil(std::vector<std::vector<double>>& grid,
11     std::vector<std::vector<double>>& new_grid, int
12     max_iterations, int rows, int cols, int block) {
13
14     for (int it = 0; it < max_iterations; ++it) {
15         for (int bj = 1; bj < cols - 1; bj +=block){
16             int jMax = std::min(bj + block, cols - 1);
17             #pragma omp parallel for
18             for (int i = 1; i < rows - 1; ++i) {
19                 for (int j = bj; j < jMax; ++j) {
20                     new_grid[i][j] = 0.25 * (grid[i-1][j] +
21 grid[i+1][j] + grid[i][j-1] + grid[i][j+1]);
22                 }
23             }
24         }
25     }
26 }

```

```
21     }
22     std::swap(grid, new_grid);
23
24 }
25 }
26
27 int main(int argc, char *argv[]) {
28     const int rows = 100; // Large number of rows
29     const int cols = 10000000; // Large number of columns
30     const int max_iterations = 1; // Maximum number of
31     iterations
32     const int block = 10000000;
33     omp_set_num_threads(1);
34     LIKWID_MARKER_INIT;
35     #pragma omp parallel
36     {
37         LIKWID_MARKER_THREADINIT;
38         LIKWID_MARKER_REGISTER("fivepoint");
39     }
40     // Initialize the grid with some values
41     std::vector<std::vector<double>> grid(rows, std::vector<
42     double>(cols, 0.0));
43     std::vector<std::vector<double>> new_grid(rows, std::vector<
44     double>(cols, 0.0));
45
46     // Initialize random number generator
47     std::random_device rd;
48     std::mt19937 gen(rd());
49     std::uniform_real_distribution<double> dis(0.0, 1.0);
50
51     // Initialize the grid with random values between 0 and 1
52     for (int i = 0; i < rows; ++i) {
53         for (int j = 0; j < cols; ++j) {
54             grid[i][j] = dis(gen);
55         }
56     }
57     #pragma omp parallel
58     {
59         LIKWID_MARKER_START("fivepoint");
60         // Applying the Jacobi 5-point stencil
61         jacobi_5pt_stencil(grid, new_grid, max_iterations, rows,
62         cols, block);
63         LIKWID_MARKER_STOP("fivepoint");
64     }
65     LIKWID_MARKER_CLOSE;
66     return 0;
67 }
```

LISTING B.4: Jacobi smoothing with the five point stencil on a 2D grid

Author References

- [1] Choi et al. “A roofline model of energy”. In: *2013 IEEE 27th International Symposium on Parallel & Distributed Processing* ([2013]). URL: https://jeewhanchoi.github.io/publication/pdf/energy_roofline.pdf.
- [2] Gottschlag and Bellosa. “Reducing AVX-Induced Frequency Variation With Core Specialization”. In: *The 9th Workshop on Systems for Multi-core and Heterogeneous Architectures co-located with Eurosys 2019, 25-28 March 2019, Dresden, Germany* ([2019]). URL: <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/1000120628>.
- [3] Hager et al. “Exploring performance and power properties of modern multi-core chips via simple machine models”. In: *Computing Research Repository* ([2013]). URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/cpe.3180>.
- [4] Hofmann et al. “On the Accuracy and Usefulness of Analytic Energy Models for Contemporary Multicore Processors”. In: *Computing Research Repository* ([2018]). URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-92040-5_2.
- [5] Khan et al. “RAPL in Action : Experiences in Using RAPL for Power Measurements”. In: *Performance Evaluation of Computing Systems* ([2018]). URL: <https://helda.helsinki.fi/server/api/core/bitstreams/bdc6c9a5-74d4-494b-ae83-860625a665ce/content>.
- [6] Laukemann et al. “CloverLeaf on Intel Multi-Core CPUs: A Case Study in Write-Allocate Evasion”. In: *ArXiv* ([2023]). URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.04797>.
- [7] Molina et al. “High-Level Synthesis Hardware Design for FPGA-Based Accelerators: Models, Methodologies, and Frameworks”. In: *IEEE Access* ([2022]). URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9864576>.
- [8] Rauber et al. “Energy measurement, modeling, and prediction for processors with frequency scaling”. In: *The Journal of Supercomputing* ([2014]). URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11227-014-1236-4>.
- [9] Skadron et al. “Temperature-aware microarchitecture: Modeling and implementation”. In: *ACM Transactions on Architecture and Code Optimization* ([2004]). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/980152.980157>.
- [10] Vasilakis. “An Instruction Level Energy Characterization of ARM Processors”. In: *Computer Architecture and VLSI Systems (CARV) Laboratory* ([2015]). URL: <https://projects.ics.forth.gr/carv/greenvm/files/tr450.pdf>.
- [11] De Vogeleer et al. “The Energy/Frequency Convexity Rule: Modeling and Experimental Validation on Mobile Devices”. In: *Parallel Processing and Applied Mathematics* ([2014]). URL: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-642-55224-3_74.

- [12] Samuel Williams. “Roofline: An Insightful Visual Performance Model for Floating-Point Programs and Multicore Architectures”. In: *Communications of the ACM* ([2009]). URL: <https://people.eecs.berkeley.edu/~kubitron/cs252/handouts/papers/RooflineVyNoYellow.pdf>.

Online References

- [13] International Energy Agency. *Data Centres: Digitizing the Economy*. 2022. URL: <https://www.iea.org/energy-system/buildings/data-centres-and-data-transmission-networks> (visited on 2023).
- [14] AMD. *4TH GEN AMD EPYC PROCESSOR ARCHITECTURE*. 2023. URL: <https://www.amd.com/system/files/documents/4th-gen-epyc-processor-architecture-white-paper.pdf> (visited on 2023).
- [15] AMD. *AMD Infinity Architecture*. 2017. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/computer-science/server-rack> (visited on 2024).
- [16] AMD. *AMD Infinity Architecture*. 2024. URL: <https://www.amd.com/en/technologies/infinity-architecture> (visited on 2024).
- [17] ARM. *Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling*. 2024. URL: <https://developer.arm.com/documentation/100960/0100/Dynamic-Voltage-and-Frequency-Scaling> (visited on 2024).
- [18] Charlie Demerjian. *A long look at AMD's Zen 3 core and chips*. 2020. URL: <https://semiaccurate.com/2020/11/07/a-long-look-at-amds-zen-3-core-and-chips/> (visited on 2023).
- [19] Dongarra et al. *Top500 for HPL*. 2023. URL: <https://top500.org/> (visited on 2023).
- [20] Travis Downs. *Ice Lake AVX-512 Downclocking*. 2020. URL: <https://travisdowns.github.io/blog/2020/08/19/icl-avx512-freq.html> (visited on 2023).
- [21] Rob Eccles. *Switching Activity And The Unknown*. 2014. URL: <https://semiengineering.com/switching-activity-and-the-unknown> (visited on 2024).
- [22] Hager et al. *ECM Performance Model*. 2018. URL: <https://hpc.fau.de/research/ecm/> (visited on 2023).
- [23] Georg Hager. *Energy vs. performance: Introducing the Z-plot*. 2016. URL: <https://blogs.fau.de/hager/archives/7504> (visited on 2023).
- [24] Georg Hager. *Write-allocate evasion has finally arrived at Intel – or has it?* 2021. URL: <https://blogs.fau.de/hager/archives/8997> (visited on 2023).
- [25] Julian Hammer. *Layer Condition Calculator*. 2024. URL: <https://rrze-hpc.github.io/layer-condition/> (visited on 2024).
- [26] Intel. *Intel (2020). Hot Chips 32: A 2nd Generation 10nm Xeon Scalable Processor with Enhanced Performance, Workload-Aware Optimizations, and Advanced Security*. 2020. URL: https://hc32.hotchips.org/assets/program/conference/day1/HotChips2020_Server_Processors_Intel_Irma_ICX-CPU-final3.pdf (visited on 2023).
- [27] Intel. *Intel Cascade Lake Microarchitecture Overview*. 2019. URL: <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/products/platforms/details/cascade-lake.html> (visited on 2023).

-
- [28] Intel. *Thermal Design Power (TDP) in Intel® Processors*. 2023. URL: <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/support/articles/000055611/processors.html> (visited on 2023).
- [29] Askar Kopbayev. *NUMA and Cluster-on-die*. 2016. URL: <https://www.starwindsoftware.com/blog/numa-and-cluster-on-die> (visited on 2024).
- [30] Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory. *Frontier: The World's Fastest Supercomputer*. 2022. URL: <https://www.datacenterdynamics.com/en/news/does-nnsa-builds-lawrence-livermore-exascale-facility-for-el-capitan-supercomputer/> (visited on 2023).
- [31] RRZE. *LIKWID repository*. 2023. URL: <https://github.com/RRZE-HPC/likwid> (visited on 2023).
- [32] RRZE. *Machine State repository*. 2019. URL: <https://github.com/RRZE-HPC/MachineState> (visited on 2023).
- [33] Vince Weaver. *Linux support for Power Measurement Interfaces*. 2023. URL: https://web.eece.maine.edu/~vweaver/projects/rapl/rapl_support.html (visited on 2023).